

Review Paper

Faecophobic Perceptions and their influence on the acceptance of Sanitation-Derived-Products reuse in Sub-Saharan Africa: A mixed review

Mayowa Abiodun Peter-Cookey^{*1}, Lawretta Adaobi Onyekwere², Barisiale Baranu³,
and Peter Emmanuel Cookey³

1. Centre for Water and Sanitation Studies (CeWASS), Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, PMB 5080, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Email: livewithmayo@gmail.com, Phone: +2349128604175

2. Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, PMB 5080, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Email: lawretta.onyekwere1@ust.edu.ng Phone: +2348037209150

3. Centre for Water and Sanitation Studies (CeWASS), Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, PMB 5080, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Email: barisiale.baranu@ust.edu.ng

3. Centre for Water and Sanitation Studies (CeWASS), Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, PMB 5080, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Email: peter.cookey@ust.edu.ng,

*Corresponding author

Abstract: This review explores how faecophobic perceptions—deep-rooted cultural and psychological aversions to human waste—affect the acceptance of sanitation-derived products (SDPs) in Sub-Saharan Africa. Despite the proven benefits of using treated human excreta for agriculture and energy, acceptance remains low due to cultural norms, religious beliefs, and misinformation about health risks. The paper

uses a mixed-methods literature review to analyse existing studies, revealing that faecophobic attitudes are not well-defined in current research; mostly focus narrowly on farmers and lack theoretical grounding in perception studies. However, some evidence suggests that with better information, public attitudes can improve. Furthermore, there were no research studies that adequately defined faecophobic perceptions, nor were there any that effectively examined how these perceptions impacted the acceptance of SDPs and strategies to alter behaviours related to them. There is a need for perception management strategies—like education, policy, and community engagement—to improve acceptance and market demand. The review calls for targeted policies, education, and community engagement to overcome these barriers, promote acceptance, and support the growth of a sanitation-based bioeconomy. The review concludes that addressing faecophobic perceptions is essential for promoting the reuse of human excreta derived resources and products and building a sanitation-based bioeconomy in the region.

Keywords: sanitation-derived-products, human-excreta-derived-products, human-excreta-derived-materials, faecal-sludge-derived-products, human-excreta-derived-fertiliser, biogas, acceptance, reuse, sanitation (bio)economy, regenerative sanitation

Citation: Peter-Cookey M.A., Onyekwere L.A., Baranu B., Cookey P.E

Faecophobic Perceptions and their influence on the acceptance of Sanitation-Derived-Products reuse in Sub-Saharan Africa: A mixed review

J. Nwashdev 1(2) 160-207

Nigerian Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development is licensed under CC BY 4.0.
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

1.0 Introduction

Faecophobia is a deeply ingrained attitude influenced by cultural norms, beliefs, and perceived risks to health, hygiene and the environment; and it leads to strong negative perceptions about the safety and utility of human excreta, preventing

the widespread acceptance of excreta-derived (i.e., sanitation-derived-products) [SDPs]. Hesitancy to accept SDPs is often attributed to faecophobia, a psychological and cultural aversion to human faeces, which stems from deep-seated perceptions of excreta as impure, unhygienic, and hazardous to health. Cultural norms, religious beliefs, and societal taboos surrounding human excreta further reinforce these attitudes, creating significant barriers to the acceptance and use of SDPs and the resources and materials extracted from human excreta, such as nutrients for organic fertiliser (Gwari et al, 2021). Faecophobia is not just a psychological issue but also a cultural and social construct that has deep cultural roots in many societies, whereby human excreta are associated with pollution, disease, and moral impurity, which has led to stigmatisation and avoidance behaviour.

Sustainable sanitation and nutrient recovery systems have emerged as vital components in addressing global environmental, energy and food production challenges (Werkneh and Gebru, 2003; Śniatała, Al-Hazmi, Sobotka, Zhai, and Małkinia, 2024; Lohman, Trimmer, Katende, Mubasira, Nagirinya, Nsereko, Banadda, Cusick, and Guest, 2020). In recent years, there has been growing interest in the potential of reusing human excreta derived products such as compost, biosolids, biogas and biofuel, animal feed (and other forms of reuse), to address key challenges related to sanitation, food security, energy, and environmental sustainability (Śniatała, et al, 2024, Lohman, et al 2020, Eom, Oh, Cho, and Kim 2021, Moya, Parker and Sakrabani, 2019), particularly in regions with scarce resources like water and soil fertility (Warner and Jones 2018). In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), rapid population growth, urbanisation, food insecurity, water and energy scarcity, agricultural inefficiencies, and limited access to sanitation infrastructure have exacerbated sanitation challenges related to human excreta management and nutrient recycling (Berendes, Yang, Lai, Hu, and Brown, 2018). The reuse of sanitation-derived- products (SDPs), also known as human-excreta-derived-products (HEDPs), have been identified as viable solutions to these challenges which could play a crucial role in improving the region's resilience, reduce dependence on synthetic fertilisers, improve agricultural productivity, environmental sustainability and public health concerns (Buit and Jansen 2016, Banamwana, Musokew, Ntakirumana, Buregyeya, Ssempebwa, Wamuyu-Maina, and Tumwesigye, 2023, Onabanjo, Patchigolla, Wagland, Fidalgo, Kolios, McAdam, Parker, Williams, Tyrrel, and Cartmell, 2016, Mihelcic, Fry and Shaw 2011). However, despite these potential benefits, the acceptance of these products and the offshoot from their use (like food or plants grown with human faeces-derived organic fertiliser) is significantly limited across many Sub-Saharan African communities (Bznanwana et al, 2023; Okem and Odinho, 2020; Buit and Jansen, 2016), mostly by widespread psychological and cultural factors related to faecophobia, the fear and aversion to human faeces (Wolgrast, 1993).

Africa is estimated to be home to 25% of the world's population by 2050 as the fastest-growing region of the world, and Sub-Saharan Africa, which stands at 1.2 billion in 2023, will be about 2.1 billion by 2050 (UNDESA 2024). The average human produces about 128g of excreta daily (Rose, Parker, Jefferson and Cartmell 2015); when we multiply this daily production by the population of SSA by 2050 (i.e. $128\text{g} \times 2.1\text{ billion} = 26,800,000,000\text{g}$), it reveals a huge load to manage in the next 25 years. Considering that Sub-Saharan Africa already grapples with an exponential deficit in sanitation infrastructure and poor management systems for faecal matter, which pose serious public health and productivity concerns (Moya, Parker, and Sakrabani 2019, Berendes, Yang, Lai, Hu, and Brown 2018), this indicates a grievous concern for the region. However, this huge matter is also a resource that contains rich nutrients and other elements that are useful to tackle food and energy security for the growing population (Berendes et al, 2018; Heinonen-Tanski and van Wijk-Sijbesma, 2005). These elements circulate continuously in natural biogeochemical cycles that constitute the only sustainable source of soil nutrients (Heinonen-Tanski and van Wijk-Sijbesma 2005). Wolgast (1993) suggests that the average person releases annually the same amount of excreta that corresponds with the amount of fertiliser required to produce 250kg of cereal per year, which coincidentally is what the average person will consume in a year. Thus, SSA is going to be sitting on a preponderance of resources that could address most of the major challenges that

the region faces and will face. In fact, by 2030, it is estimated that Africa will produce about 4.1 billion kg per year of human excreta (Berendes et al, 2018). Management of these resources is key to ensure the achievement of SDG 2 (food security), SDG 3 (health), SDG 6 (water and sanitation), SDG 7 (energy security), SDG 11 (sustainable cities), and SDG 12 (sustainable consumption and production) (Moya et al, 2019, Berendes et al 2018).

This negative perception (faecophobia) stems from its historical association with contamination, health risks, and social taboos. This fear has resulted in a general reluctance to accept or utilise products derived from human excreta, even when they are safe and beneficial for agricultural, energy, and other purposes. These perceptions significantly influence public attitudes towards the reuse of human excreta products, thereby impeding the acceptance of these products and the growth of that sector in the sanitation economy and the larger circular bio-economy. This aversion, while protective in some contexts, has become a significant barrier to the sustainable reuse of human excreta in some societies. Cultural and religious beliefs often shape attitudes toward human excreta, as in many contexts, excreta are viewed as ritually impure or socially taboo, creating resistance to their use, even when scientifically proven to be safe. Moreover, limited public knowledge about treatment technologies and processes and their benefits exacerbates misconceptions about health risks. Thus, the acceptability of SDPs depends heavily on societal perceptions, cultural beliefs, and the level of trust in treatment processes (Sugihara 2018).

Faecophobic perceptions, in this study, are described as dispositions, conceptions, thoughts, beliefs, and feelings that are derived from personal or socio-cultural norms that yield negative responses to faeces and urine. It can be acquired from personal tendencies, religious beliefs, societal norms, issues of stigma, fear of health risks, etc. It is when human faeces evoke strong negative cultural responses that result in rejection of related interactions. Acceptance, on the other hand, is how sanitation-derived products (resources) or human excreta-derived products are perceived after actual use. It relates to the individual's actual use of the product; while acceptability is a person's perception of sanitation-derived products (resources) or human excreta-derived products before they use them. It is the anticipated willingness or "a positive attitude toward adoption or willingness to consume byproducts derived from the reuse of treated faecal sludge and/or urine (Okem and Odinho, 2020; Wilde et al, 2019; Raschid-Sally and Jayakody, 2018; Riech et al, 2012; Benoit, 2012). Drangert (1998a,b) used the phrase "urine blindness" as an indication of negative perceptions of the use of urine in agriculture, while Esrey et al (1998), borrowing the term faecophobia from Jenkins (1999), to describe the muslim community's fear of human faeces.

The use of SDPs, such as compost, biosolids, and biogas, offers a promising solution to critical challenges in Sub-Saharan Africa, including poor sanitation, water scarcity, soil degradation, and the need for alternative sources of energy (Gwara et al, 2021). However, the widespread reluctance to adopt these practices is deeply rooted in faecophobic perceptions—fears, taboos, and negative attitudes towards human excreta and urine. In many Sub-Saharan African cultures, human excreta are stigmatised as dirty, impure, and associated with disease, leading to strong aversions to their reuse in agriculture, energy generation, or waste management. This persistent faecophobia hinders the acceptance of safe, effective, and sustainable technologies that recycle human waste into valuable resources, despite their potential to improve food security, reduce environmental pollution, and enhance public health (Eom et al, 2021; Khalid, 2018).

The lack of widespread acceptance of SDPs in the region impedes efforts to implement sustainable and regenerative sanitation management practices and achieve long-term sanitation and environmental goals (Gwara et al, 2021). As a result, traditional methods of excreta disposal continue to be prioritised, exacerbating challenges such as water contamination, soil fertility depletion, and dependence on chemical fertilisers. While advancements in waste treatment technologies have made the use of human excreta safe, the psychological, cultural, and social barriers to acceptance

remain substantial. Therefore, there is an urgent need to better understand the root causes of these faecophobic perceptions in Sub-Saharan Africa, identify the factors influencing public attitudes towards SDPs, and develop targeted strategies to overcome these perceptions. Addressing these challenges is critical for enabling the region to fully harness the potential of human excreta recycling for sustainable development and improving the quality of life for its populations.

The Purpose of this exploratory integrative review paper is to explore, describe, and synthesise to better understand the descriptions, definitions, findings, and emerging trends from past studies concerning faecophobic perceptions and the acceptance of SDPs in Sub-Saharan Africa, and their potential to act as a behaviour change driver. The intention is to be able to propose areas of future research, policymaking and intervention practice for perception and behaviour change strategies. As already indicated, the growing recognition of human excreta as a valuable resource for improving agricultural productivity, energy generation, and environmental sustainability is being hindered by the widespread aversion to human faeces (rooted in psychological, cultural, and social factors), and remains a significant barrier to the adoption of such practices in the region and to a sanitation (bio)economy.

As the region faces pressing issues such as inadequate sanitation, water scarcity, food insecurity, and environmental degradation, the reuse of human excreta for purposes like composting, biogas production, and fertiliser offers a sustainable and cost-effective solution. However, these solutions cannot be fully realised unless the widespread faecophobic perceptions that limit their acceptance are addressed. By highlighting the role of faecophobic perceptions, this paper emphasises how deeply ingrained fears and social stigmas surrounding human waste contribute to resistance against potentially transformative solutions and technologies. By providing a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between faecophobic perceptions and the acceptance of excreta-based products, this paper aims to contribute to the development of more effective policies, interventions, and technologies that can facilitate the sustainable reuse of human waste in Sub-Saharan Africa. Ultimately, the findings and insights presented in this paper are significant not only for advancing scientific knowledge about faecophobia but also for enabling Sub-Saharan Africa to more effectively tackle its sanitation and environmental challenges. Promoting the acceptance of human-derived excreta products is essential for improving public health, advancing food security, energy access, and sustainable agriculture, and contributing to the achievement of global sustainability goals. Therefore, the significance of this paper lies in its potential to support both local and regional efforts toward more sustainable, resilient, and equitable development in Sub-Saharan Africa. The following objectives will guide the investigations of this paper: determine how faecophobic perceptions and sanitation-derived-resources are described in literature; identify the categories of faecophobic perceptions and sanitation-derived-resources identified in literature; identify the types of sanitation-derived-resources reuse identified in literature; and determine the acceptability and acceptance levels for sanitation-derived-resources in Sub-Saharan Africa.

2.0 Background

The history of faecophobia and the acceptability of human-excreta-derived products is deeply rooted in human civilisation, shaped by cultural, religious, and scientific developments over time. In ancient societies, human excreta were often seen as both a resource and a risk, as observed in civilisations like China, Rome, and Indonesia (Gwara et al, 2021; Zeldovich, 2021a,b). Religious and cultural influences led to stigmatisation and social taboos around excreta, stemming from the belief that excreta are impure and require strict handling practices (Miller 2012). In medieval Europe, excreta management was minimal, leading to unsanitary conditions that caused widespread diseases such as cholera and typhoid (Sugihara 2018); these conditions contributed to negative associations with human excreta, reinforcing fear and avoidance. The Industrial Revolution brought rapid urbanisation and a growing population, which led to significant challenges in excreta management and public health crises, further embedding the idea of excreta as dirty and dangerous.

The advent of sewer systems prioritised disposal over reuse, effectively removing waste from sight and mind (The Water Page, 2024).

The 20th century saw significant advancements in sanitation technologies and public health awareness, but the focus remained on removal rather than reuse. The widespread adoption of synthetic fertilisers reduced reliance on excreta as a resource, diminishing its acceptability in agricultural contexts. Faecophobic perceptions have influenced a lot of attitudes, responses and interventions that have to do with excreta and sanitation management throughout civilisation, as has been indicated in previous sections. There are some areas where they have particularly shaped behaviour, policy and societal norms, and in turn, form barriers to accepting the reuse of SDPs.

Faecophobia was a driving force behind the development of sanitation infrastructure, such as flush toilets, sewage systems, and treatment plants. The historical spread of waterborne diseases like cholera and typhoid galvanised sanitation reforms during the 19th century, including the widespread construction of underground sewer systems in cities such as London (Tomes, 98), and societal aversion to human waste has historically motivated efforts to separate people from exposure to faeces to prevent diseases. Fear of faecal contamination as a vector for disease remains a key motivator behind hygiene Campaigns today (Curtis et al, 2011). Initiatives by organisations like the World Health Organisation (WHO) and United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) promote proper sanitation practices, often capitalising on faecophobic tendencies to encourage hygienic behaviours, such as washing hands after defecation and building latrines, particularly in low-income countries, to reduce the spread of related diseases. Studies show that faecophobic messaging leveraging disgust (e.g. associating Faecal contamination with uncleanness) is more effective in driving behaviour change than rational health education alone (Curtis and Cairncross, 2003). In addition, societies and cultures view topics related to defecation as shameful and embarrassing, and open discussions are taboo. This has contributed to a lack of awareness about bowel health and sanitation, which often leads to delayed treatment and diagnoses (Rosenblatt et al, 2015). This has also led to euphemisms that reflect faecophobic attitudes with words like "restroom" or "convenience" or "bathroom" masking the subject of defecation. In some religious traditions, faeces are associated with impurity, sin, or contamination, influencing practices as ritual cleansing and dietary restrictions. For instance, Hinduism considers faeces as ritual pollution, necessitating acts of cleansing after defecation (Chopra 2006). Similarly, Jewish, Christian and Islamic norms prescribe specific hygiene practices to maintain ritual cleanliness and purity, further reflecting a faecophobic worldview (Beekman, 2019).

As aforementioned, faecophobic perceptions also often hinder acceptance of sustainable sanitation practices like composting (e.g., compost toilets). Many people resist these options due to their discomfort with handling or being near excreta, and perceptions of it as unclean, despite evidence of environmental and agricultural benefits (Mehlhart and Blischwitz, 2007). Modern sanitation systems that aim to remove excreta from sight and reduce human exposure, often contribute and create environmental issues, such as untreated sewage and faecal matter and nutrient overloads in waterways, which lead to algal blooms and biodiversity loss, reflecting the unintended consequences of "flushing away" sanitation matter out of sight (Corcoran et al 2010). Faecophobia is deeply tied to the emotions, where disgust serves as a mechanism to avoid pathogen exposure. The aversion to faeces serves as a protective function, reducing the likelihood of contact with harmful bacteria and parasites. Rozen et al (2000) suggest that faeces are among the most universally recognised disgust triggers across all cultures, due to their association with harmful bacteria and parasites. This innate reaction shapes behaviours, from avoiding contamination to excessive cleanliness.

Barriers to the reuse of human-derived excreta products are largely shaped by faecophobic perceptions, which stem from cultural taboos, psychological aversion, and misconceptions about health risks. Many societies view human waste

as dirty, dangerous, and unacceptable for reuse, leading to resistance even when scientific evidence supports its safe and beneficial application in agriculture (Mara, 2013). This aversion is further reinforced by inadequate public awareness and education about the effectiveness of proper treatment processes, such as composting and pasteurisation, which eliminate pathogens and transform waste into valuable resources (Schönning & Stenström, 2004). Institutional and regulatory challenges also play a role, as sanitation policies often favour conventional waste disposal over circular sanitation models, limiting opportunities for implementation (Cordell et al., 2009). Addressing these barriers requires targeted public education, supportive policies, and successful demonstration projects to change perceptions and promote acceptance of human-derived excreta reuse. However, growing awareness of sustainability and resource recovery, as well as the global need for infinite resources, has renewed interest in the reuse of human excreta. Innovations such as composting toilets, ecological sanitation (EcoSan) systems, anaerobic digesters, and other faecal sludge treatment systems have demonstrated the potential of excreta-derived products in agriculture, energy, and water recycling (Harder, Wielemaker, Larsen, Zeeman, and Oberg, 2019). Despite these advancements, persistent faecophobic perceptions continue to hinder the acceptance and use of such products.

2.1 Faecophobic Perceptions and SDPs acceptance in Sub-Saharan Africa

Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) faces significant challenges related to sanitation, food and energy security, water access and environmental degradation. In SSA, the lack of adequate sanitation facilities, coupled with rapid population and urbanisation, poor sanitation management practices, and environmental degradation, exacerbates public health risks and hinders sustainable development (Gwara et al, 2021). Open defecation, inadequate disposal of human excreta and untreated sanitation matter contribute to the contamination of water sources and the spread of sanitation-related diseases such as cholera, dysentery, malaria, and typhoid among others (Saleem, Burdett and Heaslip 2019, Mara, 2017). The region has one of the world's lowest rates of access to improved sanitation, with over 500 million people practising open defecation or using unimproved sanitation facilities (Belay, Asraties, Aragaw, Tsega, Endalew, and Gashaw, 2022). At the same time, many parts of SSA suffer from declining soil fertility (Vanique, Six, Sanginga, and Adesina, 2015), and farmers often have limited access to chemical fertilisers due to high costs and inadequate distribution networks (Raimi, Adeleke, and Roopnaran, 2017), which threatens food security. These situations create a pressing need for alternative and locally available nutrient sources to improve agricultural productivity. In addition, energy is another major challenge in SSA, with nearly 600 million people lacking access to electricity and relying on traditional biomass for cooking (African Energy Outlook (AEO), 2022; Onabanjo et al, 2016).

Human excreta, when safely and properly treated, offer sustainable solutions to these challenges as they contain essential nutrients (e.g. phosphorous, nitrogen and potassium), which are crucial for plant growth (Hafner et al 2023, Druncker et al, 2007), and can provide a renewable energy source that can reduce dependence on firewood, alleviate deforestation, and decrease indoor air pollution (Singh et al, 2023, Kabiyi and Olanrewaju, 2022, AEO, 2022, Onabanjo et al, 2016, Subedi et al 2014, Surendra et al, 2014). The benefits of the use of human excreta for animal feed also support aquaculture and animal husbandry and, by extension, food security (Edwards 2006, 1992, Adetumbi, 2023, Onada and Ogunola, 2016); in addition, horticulture and ornamental plant growth will also benefit from these resources (Vancton Broek et al, 2024, Heinonen-Tanski and Wijk-Sijbesma, 2004, Timmer and Visker, 1998). Also, sanitation-derived biochar in place of coal for cooking and other purposes and briquettes for construction are other benefits like improving soil fertility, which could promote waste reduction, generate usable energy and enhance soil quality (Mwamilima et al, 2023, Ferronato, Mendoza, Portillo, Conti, F., and Torretta, 2022). All of these sustainable solutions could also reduce the overload of human excreta for management and, in turn, reduce public health risks of exposure and environmental degradation.

However, prevailing faecophobic perceptions in many communities pose a significant barrier to the acceptance and adoption of SDP reuse in SSA. The fear and disgust often associated with human faeces usually translate into a reluctance to use human excreta for any direct contact purposes like agriculture, aquaculture or energy purposes, regardless of the safety and benefits of these technologies (Banamwana et al 2023, Khalid 2018, Okem and Odinho, 2020, Roxbury et al, 2020). The persistence of these perceptions is influenced by cultural taboos, religious beliefs, perceived risks, lack of awareness and deeply ingrained psychological responses to byproducts of the human system. Winblad's faecophobia continuum has been used to describe attitudes and beliefs towards sanitation, which suggests that certain societies have mostly positive or negative attitudes towards faeces that determine uptake of sanitation interventions (Irfam and St. Jean 2021, Winblad and Simpson-Herbert 2004, Urwitutso 2008).

Perception is a powerful lens through which we view the world around us and how we interpret and respond to issues. It bears a strong influence on our behaviour, attitudes, beliefs, choices and decision-making (Ferguson 2004, Dijksterhuis and van Knippenberg 1998). Faecophobic perceptions are, therefore, summarised as the way that social structures perceive human excreta and the derived products as it relates to sociocultural fear, aversion, and disgust (Gwara et al, 2021). Perceptions influence and guide behaviour, motivate or demotivate all actions, and determine the future success of technologies and products. To manage such future success, perceptions have to be managed and applied to adapt the strategy of technology implementation and transfer to the tasks of creating, shifting, changing, and managing perceptions. It is key to have an in-depth understanding of what guides the social and mental fabrics (thoughts) that motivate people's acceptance or rejection of using SDPs for food production and other purposes (Duncker, Matsebe, Moilwa, 2007).

2.2 Faecophobic Perceptions as drivers for SDPs' acceptance in SSA

Faecophobic perceptions could include sociocultural and religious taboos as well as psychological factors that hinder the acceptance of SDPs and related technologies (Built and Jansen, 2018; Banamwana et al, 2023; Booth et al, 2017; Gwara et al, 2021; Curtis et al, 2005). Several studies have explored the psychological and cultural factors that contribute to faecophobic perceptions. Faecophobia is not only a psychological phenomenon but also a socially constructed aversion shaped by cultural norms, taboos, and historical associations with human excreta. Many African societies and cultures view human excreta as impure or spiritually unclean, associating it with pollution and moral decay. Booth et al (2017) emphasise that in SSA, these FPs act as strong barriers to adopting any form of human excreta for reuse, whether treated or not. The strong psychological reaction of disgust towards human excreta is a universal human response, which Rozin et al (2008) explain plays a critical role in faecophobia. In societies where human excreta are seen as a source of contamination and disease, disgust reactions are heightened, especially where sanitation infrastructure is lacking, and human excreta are associated with disease and poor hygiene. These FPs will outweigh rational assessments of risk and safety, according to Schwank et al (2018), leading to an ingrained fear of reuse, which makes it even difficult to accept reuse technologies as well (Gilbert et al, 2013; Curtis et al, 2011). Perceived risks are another FP that hinders acceptance of SDPs and their related technologies (Schwank et al, 2018) highlighted. In addition, Verbyla et al (2014) show in their study that perceived risks often differ from actual risks (Slovic 1999), and despite empirical evidence of safe treatment, some African societies remain sceptical. Furthermore, social norms that promote the avoidance of human excreta perpetuate faecophobia. Kasperon et al (2003) Social Amplification of Risk Framework suggests that social networks and media can amplify fears and misinformation about human excreta reuse. In many SSA cultures, there is a stigma attached to activities that involve human excreta, particularly those involving food production and energy generation. Some rural African communities even avoid using SDP composts due to fear of being socially ostracised (Sibanda et al, 2019; Banamwana et al, 2023; Sonneveld et al, 2018).

Figure 1 Map of Sub Saharan countries (Source: USDA Economic Research Service - https://ers.usda.gov/sites/default/files/_laserfiche/Charts/104806/SSACovid_Fig01.png?v=77756)

The acceptance of human-derived excreta products in Sub-Saharan Africa is heavily influenced by faecophobic perceptions, which are shaped by cultural, psychological, and social factors. These perceptions present a significant barrier to the adoption of technologies that can transform human waste into valuable resources for agriculture, energy, and sanitation. However, evidence suggests that these barriers can be overcome through education, community engagement, technological innovation, and strategic policy development. By addressing faecophobia head-on and reframing the public discourse around the safe and beneficial use of human excreta, Sub-Saharan Africa can unlock the potential of waste reuse technologies to promote sustainable development, enhance food security, and improve public health.

In summary, the literature on faecophobic perceptions and the acceptance of SDPs in Sub-Saharan Africa underscores the complex interplay of cultural, psychological, social, and technological factors. Faecophobia, shaped by deep cultural taboos and psychological aversions, remains a significant barrier to the adoption of human waste reuse technologies. However, evidence suggests that education, community involvement, and technological adaptations that reduce perceived risks and emphasise the benefits of human excreta products can help overcome these barriers (Mabhaudhi et al, 2019; Schwank et al, 2018). By addressing both the psychological and social dimensions of faecophobia, it is possible to pave the way for more sustainable and innovative waste management solutions in Sub-Saharan Africa.

In short, Sub-Saharan Africa is confronted with severe sanitation management issues, including inadequate access to clean water and sanitation facilities, widespread open defecation, and the contamination of water resources, which exacerbate public health risks and environmental pollution. The safe reuse of human excreta products such as compost, biosolids, and biogas has the potential to offer sustainable solutions to these challenges. At the same time, human excreta

represent a vast untapped resource for improving soil fertility, generating biogas, and reducing reliance on chemical fertilisers, which are often expensive and environmentally damaging. These products can contribute to improving soil fertility, increasing agricultural productivity, generating renewable energy, and reducing dependence on chemical fertilisers, all of which are essential for enhancing food security and resilience to climate change. However, despite the technological advances that have made the reuse of human excreta both safe and effective, the fear and taboo surrounding human excreta persist as significant barriers to their adoption. Therefore, overcoming the cultural and psychological barriers to the acceptance of these products and technologies is not just a matter of convenience but a necessity for achieving sustainable development.

A growing body of literature highlights both the potential benefits of using human excreta for agricultural and energy purposes and the significant psychological and cultural barriers that hinder acceptance; however, only a few have directly identified and addressed the issue of faecophobic perceptions in Sub-Saharan Africa. This literature review examines key studies and findings that shed light on the complexities of faecophobia and its role in shaping public attitudes towards human waste-derived products in the region. Thus, this mixed review aims to assess the role faecophobic perceptions play in the acceptance of SDPs (that is, human faeces-derived products) and the related technologies in SSA communities. Many review studies have looked at issues of excreta disgust and how it affects reuse of SDPs and new sanitation technology like Ecosan in SSA, but none have looked at the effect or role of faecophobic perceptions as a barrier to accepting reuse of SDPs. Thus, this review paper is critical to highlighting the role of faecophobia in the acceptance of SDPs and related technologies (Gwara et al, 2021; Harder et al, 2019; Hukari et al, 2016). Most studies also focus on the reuse of SDP nutrients in agriculture, predominantly by farmers (Gwara et al, 2022, 2021, 2020, King, 2021).

The rationale for this review paper stems from the urgent need to address the barriers that hinder the widespread acceptance and adoption of SDPs and related technologies in Sub-Saharan Africa, a region that faces pressing challenges related to sanitation, food security, environmental sustainability, and resource scarcity (Gwara et al, 2021). Despite the potential benefits of utilising human excreta for food production, energy, and waste management purposes, these deep-rooted faecophobic perceptions—fuelled by cultural taboos, psychological disgust, and social stigma—remain a significant obstacle to realising these benefits and to widespread acceptance and adoption of these solutions. The persistence of these perceptions limits the potential of SDPs to contribute to solving pressing regional issues such as food insecurity, water scarcity, energy access, and environmental degradation.

Thus, the justification for this paper is also based on the growing global recognition of the importance of circular economy principles, which emphasise resource recycling and waste-to-resource initiatives. In Sub-Saharan Africa, where resources are often scarce and sanitation challenges are acute, the adoption of sanitation-derived products presents an innovative solution to multiple interconnected problems. Understanding the psychological, cultural, and social roots of faecophobia in Sub-Saharan Africa is crucial to overcoming hindering barriers. Furthermore, understanding the factors that influence public perceptions and behaviour is crucial for designing targeted, context-sensitive interventions that consider both the cultural sensitivities and technological needs of local communities. Also, the effective promotion of SDPs requires not only the development of safe and sustainable technologies but also an understanding of how to shift public perceptions and engage communities in behavioural change.

Finally, this review aims to bridge the gap between the understanding of faecophobic perceptions and the influence on the acceptance of SDPs in Sub-Saharan Africa by offering insights into how attitudes, beliefs, and community norms shape acceptance. By offering a comprehensive examination of these dynamics, this paper provides valuable evidence for policymakers, development practitioners, and researchers working to design programmes that promote the safe and

effective use of human excreta-derived products. As such, this review will contribute to the development of tailored education and outreach programmes, policy frameworks, and technology adoption strategies aimed at overcoming faecophobic perceptions and fostering the acceptance of human waste reuse. This paper also has the potential to inform future research, policy development, and programmatic interventions that will enable Sub-Saharan Africa to capitalise on the benefits of products derived from human excreta, supporting broader goals of sustainable development, public health improvement, and environmental resilience. By addressing faecophobic perceptions head-on, this review aims to facilitate discussions to cause a paradigm shift in how communities in Sub-Saharan Africa view human waste and its potential as a valuable resource for a more sustainable future.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

This review employed the mixed review (which included descriptive, exploratory and integrative-see Figure 1) methodology to explore the progress of literature on the subject matter of faecophobic perceptions and how it affects the acceptance of SDPs in SSA communities. There are minimal studies that look at the concept of faecophobic perceptions, but some studies have considered the attitudes towards SDPs, particularly in agriculture, and among farmers. However, no prior reviews have bothered to define faecophobic perceptions (except the concept of faecophobia, which is the social and cultural aversion to excreta), and what acceptance of SDPs and the technologies that follow is, and if there are any direct correlations. This mixed review aims to explore the definitions, descriptions, insights, and findings drawn from previous studies concerning these key concepts and how they influence the acceptance of these SDPs. The intention is to attempt to come up with a clear definition of these concepts and a description of any connections, as well as to synthesise available knowledge to potentially gain deeper comprehension, and discover areas for future research, interventions and policy implications. The review methods are reported in a complementary combination of the PRISMA and integrative/descriptive review formats.

This mixed review study used a rigorous, iterative and detailed methodology to conduct an exploratory integrative review using the PRISMA (BMJ 2021) and Whittmore and Knafl (2005) and Russell (2005) methods complementarily with descriptive elements. This methodology allows for explorative search across diverse disciplines and fields, and the multidisciplinary synthesis of methods, data, and themes drawn from all literature reviewed. The methodology is structured and well described to ensure replicability and drastically reduce the risk of bias. It also identifies gaps in the literature for further study.

To ensure reliability, only peer-reviewed articles from journals not included on the Beall List of Predatory Journals were used (<https://bealllist.net/>). The researcher skimmed through the abstracts and full texts of the journal articles first to check their relevance for the study. The relevant data from existing journal articles were necessary to enhance the generalisability of findings (Morse 1997).

An exploratory review was first done as initial review to discover emerging patterns and trends (Vandeginste et al, 2024, Agrawal et al, 2024, Cataldo et al, 2022) as only relatively few studies exist in this area, but the phenomenon is significantly crucial for the future of sanitation management and the SDG 6, reuse of derived resources as well as the sanitation economy in Sub-Saharan African countries.

To get an understanding of the terms and concepts and how they are described in literature, a descriptive review was conducted to identify the way sanitation-derived-products (SDPs) and faecophobic perceptions (FPs) and acceptability

levels and acceptance have been described and defined in literature; and to reveal the categories and types of SDPs and FPs from literature.

In addition, to generate a well of knowledge from the reviews, an integrative review was used to enable the researcher examine multidimensional perspectives across disciplines, fields, and sectors, and to be able to triangulate and synthesise findings from quantitative and qualitative studies – mixed methods – (Cronin and George 2023, Kutcher and LeBaron 2022, Oermann and Knafl, 2022, Dhollande, Taylor, Meyer, and Scott 2021, Souza, Silva, and Carvalho, 2010, Whitemore R and Knafl K. 2005) and increase the validity of the research (Onwugbuezie and Johnson 2006). This has been known to provide an in-depth understanding of complex phenomena.

Figure 2 Mixed Review Format

This review was conducted in an iterative manner that applied detailed rigour and explicit strategies drawn from the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Page et al., 2021) methodology for reviews. This enabled the researcher to blend standards for review studies to create enough rigour and validity for this mixed review to richly mine for knowledge and data. The nine stages of this review, thus, will be to categorically identify the problem, state the research question(s), search for relevant literature, state exclusion and inclusion criteria, select the most appropriate literature, extract, evaluate and analyse data, synthesise, present and discuss. The study particularly addresses the purpose and problem identified with the following research questions: (i) what is the extent of studies on faecophobic perceptions and how they influence acceptance of sanitation-derived products in Sub-Saharan Africa?, (ii) what are the categories and definitions of faecophobic perceptions, sanitation-derived products, and their reuse identified in the literature?, and (iii) how does literature express the influence of faecophobic perceptions on the acceptance of sanitation-derived products?

3.2 Search Strategy

Before developing a search strategy, a broad exploratory scope of literature was conducted to get an idea of the concepts and terms used to refer to the phenomenon, from which synonyms were collated along with keywords. To identify relevant literature, academic databases and search engines were used. A review of references in relevant literature was also further examined for more resources, which led to more key sources, and the references of these literature sources were further reviewed and analysed. This iterative process continued until there were no more articles to be gleaned. Keywords (e.g. faecophobic perceptions, sanitation-derived-products, human-excreta-derived-products/materials, human-derived-waste, human-waste, resource-oriented-sanitation, acceptability levels, acceptance, excreta, urine, reuse and some other synonyms) were used in databases and search engines to find relevant sources in order not to leave out any related studies that may add to the reliability and comprehensive scope of the review.

A search strategy was conducted in April 2025 that included Google Scholar, PubMed, Zandy and Springer Nature; seven searches were conducted for each database. Table 1 shows the search strings used with terms such as faecophobic, perception, sanitation, reuse, human excreta, urine, faeces, faecal sludge, acceptance and acceptability, among others; Sub-Saharan Africa was added to each search after exhausting the derivations. Using relevant keywords, related key words were combined like “faecophobic perceptions”, “sanitation-derived-resources”, “human-derived-waste-products”, “resource oriented sanitation”, “excreta disgust”, and human faeces based”; synonyms were also included like utilisation, excreta, urine, acceptance and willingness; differentiations in spelling were also considered. Boolean operators “AND”, “OR” and truncation (“NOT”) to create search strings (see Table 1). After eliminating the duplicates across all searches, relevant articles were identified by screening titles, abstracts and some full texts. Eligibility was determined by assessing the full texts and abstracts of the remaining sources and further screened for relevance in terms of their focus, objectives. Finally, references in the articles were gleaned by the researcher for additional studies related to the research question of this review. Searches were also conducted on the Google search engine. To ensure that no related study was left out, some studies gleaned from references that hinted at faecophobia or perceptions aligned with the reuse of SDPs were also included, including studies done in non-SSA countries.

Table 1: Applied Search strings

Search String	Number of papers retrieved
sanitation OR “faecal sludge” OR excreta or urine OR faeces* OR *human waste* OR *human manure* OR shit OR poo	193,982
“sanitation derived products” OR “sanitation derived resources” OR “human waste derived products” OR “human excreta derived products” OR “human faeces based” OR “resource oriented sanitation”	10,675
faecophobic OR faecophobia OR “excreta disgust”	323
perception OR attitude OR behaviour OR belief OR acceptance OR acceptability	4,898,431
“faecophobic perception” OR “excreta disgust” AND attitude OR behaviour OR belief	2,645,037
“faecophobic perception” OR “excreta disgust” AND reuse OR utilisation	2,253,621
“faecophobic perception” OR “excreta disgust” sanitation AND reuse OR utilisation AND “sanitation derived products” OR “human waste derived products” OR “human waste derived products” OR “human faeces based” OR “resource oriented sanitation” OR *human waste* OR *human manure* AND acceptance OR acceptability AND “Sub Saharan Africa”	1,957

The rich and expansive databases of Scopus, Web of Science and PsychINFO were inaccessible because the researcher's institution was not registered on them. This could have led to some key articles being left out of the study. But the databases and search engines that were used were well saturated and references curated to yield a good sample.

3.3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The searches only included articles in English and only peer-reviewed journals, across all disciplines and fields that were published between January 2014 to April 2025. No restriction on study design and duration was applied. Quantitative and qualitative methodologies were included. The final search resulted in over 1000 articles; thus, screening full texts and abstracts excluded about 768 articles that were irrelevant to the subject matter. Papers that did not refer to the reuse of sanitation-derived or human waste or excreta-derived products were excluded, and papers that did not consider perceptions of disgust or related faecophobic perceptions and acceptability or acceptance were also excluded. Dissertations, editorials, opinions, theses, reports, and conference papers were also excluded, but used to garner more insights in the discussions. Subsequently, duplicate papers were removed.

3.4 Data Extraction and Analysis

Studies were assessed according to: author, publication date, country, sample size and population, context/setting, theory (or whether) used, study design, objectives, scope, type of SDP investigated, faecophobic perceptions identified, factors influencing acceptance or barriers to acceptance, findings/results.

Relevant data (based on the three different types of reviews) were extracted from 40 articles selected (Table 2) after all inclusion and exclusion criteria were fulfilled, and duplicates were removed. Also, some titles could not be retrieved for abstract and/or full text screening, and were thus not included in the final review. A standard data extraction matrix (Table 5) that captured key information from the selected articles was developed, and a synthesised version was presented in this paper. The data extracted included the following:

Table 2: Data Extraction Process Search String

Exploratory	Descriptive	Integrative
Year of Publication	Type of Study	Country/Region and Setting of Study (urban, rural, household, farm, community, etc.)
Objective of the Study	Country/Region and Setting of Study (urban, rural, household, etc.)	Study Design (quan, qual and mixed)
Author(s) Location	Definitions and Descriptions	Data Collection Methodology
Author(s) Discipline	Study Design (quan, qual and mixed)	Research Instruments used
Author(s) Affiliations	Conceptual and Theoretical Framework	Participant Sample
Geographical Location and Setting of Study	Main Findings	Conceptual and Theoretical Framework
Data Collection Methodology		Expected Outcome
Research Instruments used		Main Findings
Participant Sample		
Tools for measuring perception and acceptance		

Quantitative, qualitative and mixed findings were synthesised and presented in narrative and graphical format, but no meta-analysis was conducted due to the differences in methods and indicators. No quality assessments were carried out because the researcher assumed that, since most of the articles were drawn from the list of highest ranking in the databases, they were of good quality. However, this could be a limitation in the quality of the studies.

3.5 Data Synthesis

Data was synthesised by presenting research questions in thematic formats, and the synthesis involved a convergence of the findings from the three different reviews. In addition, the reviews included quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods studies; all these findings were also synthesised to provide a comprehensive result. The paper aims to present a comprehensive overview and describe the relevant concepts by combining, integrating, and synthesising findings to

identify emerging patterns and trends, and the extent of research in the subject area. The synthesis of the results was done by triangulation of the findings of the reviews and the findings extracted from the different methods of the selected studies. Conclusions were drawn by synthesising the observed patterns and connections to propose a possible perception management strategy for sanitation-derived resources, and to determine possible areas for future research. The study looked generally at SDPs, but did not specifically address types of SDPs to see which is more likely to be accepted and used. This is also a gap in the reviewed literature and an area for future research.

4.0 Results

This mixed review identified a total of 1957 articles; 39 duplicate articles were removed, and another 768 articles were also removed due to not being focused on faecal sludge, Sub-Saharan Africa, perception or acceptability/acceptance. In essence, a total of 807 were removed before screening. Title and abstract screening removed 367 articles, while full text initial screening removed 136 articles, making a total of 503 articles removed. Further screening for inclusion and exclusion criteria removed 372 articles; this left 275 articles. Out of these 275 articles, 199 could not be retrieved due to inaccessibility or other restrictions. Thus, 76 articles were assessed for eligibility. During data extraction, another 36 articles were removed at full text review, which left a total of 40 that met the final criteria for the review (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 PRISMA Flow Chart for the Search Strategy

4.1 Characteristics of Articles Included

40 articles were selected, and 26 of them were studies on SSA, 10 in Asia, 4 in Europe, 4 in the Americas (South and North), and 2 in the Middle East. Even though the focus of the study is SSA, it helped to understand the extent of research on the phenomenon by looking at other regions as well. Two of the articles (Simha et al, 2021; Conroy and Mancini, 2022) covered more than 10 countries across Africa, Asia, Europe, and the Americas (see Figure 3). In total, these studies covered about 37 countries with South Africa having the most studies (8), followed by Ghana and Uganda at 5 studies each, while Madagascar, Morocco and Nigeria had only one study each (Figure 4). 24 of these countries were developing countries which is at about 61.5% of the total publications studied indicating a serious issue of reusing SDPs as alternative to vital but finite resources for food and energy.

Figure 3: Number of Publications by Region

Figure 4: Number of Publications by Country of Study

Figure 5: Number of publications by Methodology/Study Design

Most of the studies used mixed methods (15 of them), while quantitative and qualitative alone were 9 studies each, and there were six review studies (two were scoping reviews (Gwara et al 2021, Gwara et al, 2020) while the others did not categorise their review methodology (Figure 5). Meanwhile, surveys, interviews and focus group discussions were the most deployed data collection instruments, as well as scientific experiments on soil and crop. Studies were equally distributed between urban and rural settings (16 studies each), which were the highest (Figure 6), while 21 studies particularly targeted sample participants who were farmers or related, like Gardeners, farming communities and farmers' cooperative organisations, with a total of over 6000 respondents. One study focused on muslim studies in Bangladesh and the sociocultural acceptance of urine-diverting dry toilets (UDDTs). Households, universities, peri-urban and slum settings were the other contexts considered; apart from review papers, which focused on subject matter rather than just a setting or particular group of people, although Gwara et al 2021 did focus on farmers (Figure 6). A lot of the studies did not properly describe or clearly state their study design and methodology, as some sample sizes were not stated or unclear, and the study design was too ambiguous, which could affect replication.

Figure 6: Number of Publications by Study Setting/Context

Most studies were conducted between 2020 and 2022 (19 in all), while in the seven years before 2020 (2013-2019), there were only 17 studies, and only five studies from 2023 – 2025 (in fact, nothing in 2025) (Figure 7). This is an area that has not quite caught up in the research arena, even though it is a significant issue. It is, however, possible that some studies were missed because the researchers did not have access to Scopus and other major databases, and also considering that faecophobic perceptions have not been a focus in research. Some studies had been conducted before 2013, but were not included in this review as they go way back (e.g. Duncker et al, 2007).

These articles were published in over 34 journals domiciled across major publishers (Elsevier, Taylor and Francis, Wiley, MDPI, Springer, Nature, etc – see Box 1). Authors came from a myriad of disciplines (Figure 9), indicating the multi- and inter-disciplinary nature of the phenomenon. Only about 9 authors were from the social sciences disciplines and behavioural science field, even though these were studies on perception, attitude, intentions and behaviour. Others were from engineering (25), environmental management (18), agriculture (15), crop and soil sciences (17), and other disciplines, and only one was in the water and sanitation field.

Figure 7: Timeline of Publications by Year of Study

These articles were published in over 34 journals domiciled across major publishers (Elsevier, Taylor and Francis, Wiley, MDPI, Springer, Nature, etc – see Box 1). Authors came from a myriad of disciplines (Figure 9), indicating the multi- and inter-disciplinary nature of the phenomenon. Only about 9 authors were from the social sciences disciplines and behavioural science field, even though these were studies on perception, attitude, intentions and behaviour. Others were from engineering (25), environmental management (18), agriculture (15), crop and soil sciences (17), and other disciplines, and only one was in the water and sanitation field.

Box 1: Journals that published included articles.

Springer Nature, Cities and Health, Nature Portfolio, Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development, Resources, Conservation and Recycling, Environment, Development and Sustainability, Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics, Sustainability, Waste Biomass Valorisation, Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems, International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, PLOS One, Science of Total , Agriculture, Journal of Water Reuse and Desalination, Energy Research and Social Science, Water Research, Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments, Mundo Amazonico, Water and Environment Journal and Human Organization, Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences, Africa Health Sciences, Nature Portfolio-Scientific Reports, Hygiene and Environmental Health Advances, Food Policy, Energy Research & Social Science, International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development, Sustainable Environment, Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments, Journal of Cleaner Production, Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development

Figure 8: Number of publications by Authors' Discipline/Field

Together, the studies included about 20,000 participants (most of whom were farmers) and maximum was 3763 and a minimum was 5 (Table 4); although not all studies were clear about their sample size, and some review papers did not indicate the number of studies that were reviewed (Table 4). Six of the articles were review papers (van den Broek 2024, Conroy and Mancini, 2022, Gwara et al, 2021, Gwara et al, 2020, Sugihara, 2018, Roma et al, 2013). Most of the reviews focused on the reuse of human excreta (i.e. faeces and urine) in agriculture as fertiliser and soil conditioners, while one (Conroy and Mancini, 2022) addressed the use of UDDTs and by-products in middle and low-income countries. The sampling method was predominantly random and purposive. Thematic analysis and coding were predominant.

Table 4: Number of publications by Sample size and Population

Sample Population	Sample Size	No. of Publications
Farmers/Farmer Producer Organisations	6528	21
University/School/Research Community	4470	8
User community	310	1
Bioenergy Entrepreneurs	50	1
Traders	59	1
Pit Emptiers	41	1
Garden owners	326	2
Non-Garden owners	247	1
Households	18929	8
Residents/ Citizens/Public	1892	5
Fertiliser Retailers	15	1
Food Retailers	127	1
Online	4112	2
Literature	60	6
Others (unspecified)	63	3

The predominant frameworks were Theory of Planned Behaviour, New Ecological Paradigm and Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Framework (Box 2). Most of the papers did not anchor their studies on any theoretical or conceptual framework, although many of them mentioned the Disgust Theory (Rozin, Haidt and Macaulay, 2000) to back up their claims of excreta aversion. Nevertheless, the majority of those with theoretical backgrounds used the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ejigu and Yeshitela, 2024; Simha et al, 2021; Gwara et al, 2021; Osei-Marfo et al, 2021; Simha et al, 2018; Ignacio et al, 2018; Lagerkvist et al., 2015), Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) (Ejigu and Yeshitela, 2024, Ignacio et al, 2018), or a combination of both (Ejigu and Yeshitela, 2024, Ignacio et al, 2018). These studies in particular also included the New Ecological Paradigm to address how environmental dispositions affect perceptions and attitudes in SDPs' reuse acceptance (Gwara et al, 2022, 2021, Simha et al, 2018). The Diffusion of Innovation Theory were mainly used for perceptions of technology or SDPs from technology like UDDT, etc (Conroy and Mancini, 2022; Gitau et al, 2020). While another paper anchored their study on several theories and concepts like contagion, pathogen sensitivity, disgust, risk perception and judgement, perceived risk and benefits, attitude and associated behaviours, and the role of affect in judgement (Ekane et al, 2015), Mkude et al, (2021) and Nimoh et al, 2014 used the Knowledge, Attitudes and Practice framework (KAP), although Nimoh et al, (2014) called theirs the Knowledge Attitude and Perception framework while referring to the KAP framework. Banamwana et al (2023) proposed the Adaptive Excreta Disgust Theory based on the Rozin-Haidt-Macauley Model and Grounded Theory; however, it was not clearly described. Van den Broek et al (2024) anchored their work on the Sanitation Focus Opportunity Ability and Motivation (SANIFOAM) framework (Devine 2009) of the World Bank. It is interesting to note that although most of these studies were on perception and attitudes, with over 18 of them with these terms in their titles, there was no theory or conceptual understanding of social and individual perceptions through related theories like the Social Perception Theory (Ferguson 2004).

Box 2 Types of Conceptual and Theoretical Frameworks applied (Many did not have anchoring theories and/or frameworks)

Conceptual and Theoretical Frameworks applied.

- Diffusion of Innovation (3 studies)
- Social Cognitive Theory/Social Psychology Theory (1 study)
- Theory of Planned Behaviour*** (6 studies)
- Theory of Reasoned Action (2 studies)
- Technology Acceptance Model** (4 studies)
- Contingent Valuation (1 study)
- New Ecological Paradigm* (3 studies)
- Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) (2 studies)
- Sanitation Focus Opportunity Ability and Motivation (SaniFOAM) (1 study)
- Combined Model of Theory of Planned Behaviour and Technology Acceptance Model (C-TBP-TAM) (2 studies)
- Grounded Theory (1 study)
- Rozin-Haidt-McCauley Model (1 study)
- Interpretivist Paradigm/Afrocentric Paradigm (1 study)
- Campbell (1963) Attitude and associated Behaviours (1 study)
- Contagion, Disgust, Revulsion and Pathogen Sensitivity (1 study)
- Risk Perception and Judgement (1 study)
- Role of Affect in Judgement and Decision-making (1 study)
- Relationship between Perceived Risks and Benefits (1 study)
- Receptivity Model (1 study)

4.2 Definitions and Types of FPs and SDPs

Despite over 40% of the papers having perception or related terms (like attitudes) in their titles and objectives, almost none defined perception and its effects on Behaviour, decision-making and choice-making, and intentions. Many mentioned faecophobia, but failed to adequately define it and relate it to perceptions related to reactions to excreta.

One paper mentioned along the way that perception can influence decisions and actions (Gwara et al, 2021). Khalid (2018) suggests that perceptions and ideas about what is dirty associated with daily habits greatly influence the way people approach sanitation, but did not exactly explain that concept of perception. Lagerkvist et al (2015) defined attitudes and concluded that the formation of attitudes depends on memory representations that had been previously stored, and that attitudes can be inferred from actual behaviours. Wilde et al (2022), on the other hand, defined attitude as "the degree of a person's favourable or unfavourable evaluation or appraisal of a Behaviour or question (derived from Ajzen 1991, p.188). Some papers did attempt to refer to risk and benefits perceptions and went on to describe the perception of excreta disgust, which is a faecophobic perception; but they did not expressly address the concept as a perception issue, more of an avoidance one (Banamwana et al, 2023, Ekane et al, 2015).

In addition, some of the studies mentioned faecophobia and gave very brief descriptions without exactly pointing them out as perceptions, even though the titles and objectives claim to explore or investigate perceptions. None identified anti-excreta reuse as perceptions or acceptance barriers identified, and none connected faecophobia to the issues they identified even though some of these perceptions (such as excreta disgust, fear of disease/infection, fear of contamination/pollution, fear of exposure/contact, and other sociocultural factors could be attributed as faecophobic perceptions as they are related to faecophobia - which is the disgust, fear and aversion associated with human excreta in a society (Jenkins 1999, Gwara et al 2021). However, Buit and Jansen (2016) had the term 'fecophoby' in their paper title, but did not exactly describe the phenomenon and concentrated on negating the impression of Ghana being a faecophobic society, as some scholars had assumed. While Simha et al (2018) also described faecophobia to some extent, but did not use it to describe the perceptions identified in their study, it seemed to be just a related concept.

The sanitation-derived products (SDPs) identified in the study were derived from human (urine and excreta), whether fresh, dried, or treated and converted. Most of the studies did not categorically define or describe the SDPs under study, especially when it's just human excreta or urine, or they describe it as dried, wet or faecal sludge. Some gave a detailed description like Wilde et al (2022) on the use of nitrified urine fertiliser in agriculture, and Nicholas et al (2022) described and defined biochar and biosolids from sewage in their study on the acceptance thereof in Wales, England. Osei-Marfo (2021) and Aijeh et al (2021) also described the SDP biogas from human excreta, and McConville et al (2022) described the product and process of acquiring the SDPs (from urine) they investigated, that is, struvite, phosphorus, and dehydrated urine derived from sewage. While some papers that included the use of resource-oriented sanitation infrastructure that produced biogas or fertiliser gave detailed descriptions of the technology, like urine diverting dry toilets (UDDTs), Eco-Toilets (ETS), Smart Eco-Toilets (SETs) and Toilet-Linked Anaerobic Digesters (TLADs) and the subsequent SDP that they produced, like compost (Conroy and Mancini 2022, Eom et al 2021, Williams et al 2022, Ignacio et al 2018). However, the SDP concepts, such as different types of fertiliser, whether excreta, urine, sludge, or char/briquettes, were not particularly described to be able to have a general sense of what sanitation-derived products are and how they are derived; although their benefits were well articulated.

Most of the findings indicate that the focus was on reusing SDPs towards food security and sufficiency by providing affordable and accessible fertilisers to farmers that will be acceptable directly or indirectly, as seen in the Figure 9. The only other use for SDPs explored in the studies reviewed were for replacing human excreta derived biogas for cooking

(Williams et al 2022, Conroy and Mancini 2022, Mkude et al 2021, Osei-Marfo 2021, Aijeh et al 2020, Gitau et al 2020, Simha et al 2018), latrine treatment (Shirish et al 2022), while Eom et al (2021) covered the use of resources from Smart Eco-Toilet systems installed in households to generate bioenergy for the community and to test the willingness to install and pay for such services.

Generally, Faecophobic Perceptions (FPs) identified in the studies under review were mainly traditional excreta disgust, fear of disease/infection, fear of stigmatisation/others' opinions, and unsafe practices (Figure 10). The irrational psychological reaction of disgust when considering human excreta was identified as one of the leading perceptions of SDPs' reuse or consideration for reuse. Although it was not always considered an irredeemable barrier, it was often a major response to any exposure (even in conversations) to any product derived from human excreta or related materials (Banamwana et al, 2023; Gwara et al, 2021; Okem et al, 2013; Nicholas et al, 2022; Roxburgh et al, 2020; Khalid, 2018; Mkude et al., 2021, Gitau et al 2020, Built and Jansen 2016). Fear of stigmatisation and what others think (like neighbours, family, and customers/buyers of farm produce) ranked second in the FPs identified as even those who did not succumb to the psychological disgust reaction, yielded to the psychological reaction to exclusion from society; which could also be related to other sociocultural FPs like fears of breaking social and religious norms, and taboos. The fear of the unknown or uncertainties was also identified as probably related to a lack of knowledge about the SDPs, their treatment/safety, and health risks. Fear of soil and crop contamination/pollution by faeces, and the fear that these crops grown in soil fertiliser with SDPs may adopt the smell and taste of the original material, that is, excreta. This also includes the disgust factor that relates to fear as well as contact/exposure when people cannot stand the smell or appearance of mainly raw and wet excreta or sludge (Roxburgh et al, 2020).

Figure 9: Number of publications by Types of Sanitation-Derived-Products identified

Table 5 shows key characteristics of the articles with objectives and main findings.

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Mugivhisa and Olowoyo 2015</p> <p>FPs: perceived health risks; taboo, religion, sociocultural norms, others</p> <p>SDP: urine</p> <p>Acceptance: low to medium, with better info</p>	<p>To assess if lack of knowledge results unacceptability of human urine in agriculture by assessing their knowledge about the nutritional value of the human urine as fertilizer in South Africa; if they would eat crops fertilized with human urine; and if been provided with better information would change their attitudes and ease their fears and unwillingness.</p>	<p>Most respondents were unaware of human urine as a fertilizer and would not eat spinach and maize fertilised with urine. Health reasons were given as the main reasons for being unwilling to eat crops fertilised with human urine, followed by taboo, and minimally religion. Most were willing to change their attitudes and unwillingness if they were better informed about the safety of human urine use for agricultural purposes.</p>
<p>Mugivhisa, Olowoyo, and Mzimba, 2017</p> <p>FPs: perceived health risks; unclean, smell, unhygienic nature, disease -causing</p> <p>SDP: urine, faeces, sewage</p> <p>Acceptance: uncertain</p>	<p>Assessed subsistence farmers' perceptions of organic farming and use of organic fertilisers; how they rated the acceptability of various organic fertilisers in the production of vegetables; and whether they would consider changing their minds if they were better informed.</p>	<p>Human urine, human faeces and dry sewage were the leastfavoured type of organic fertilisers. Almost all respondents indicated that they would not use human faeces, sewage and human urine in their gardens due to smell, unhygienic nature and disease-causing potential. More than half of the respondents indicated they were willing to change their minds concerningthe use of organic fertilisers.</p>
<p>Ignacio, Malenab, Pausta, Beltran, Belo, Tanhueco, Era, Eusebio, Promentilla, and Orbecido, (2018)</p> <p>FPs: fear of disease, witchcraft, fear of breaking social norms and taboos</p> <p>SDP: human excreta</p> <p>Acceptance: low</p>	<p>Aims to explain how the community thinks towards the Eco Toilet Systems based on their perceived behavioural control (or facilitation conditions) and subjective norms.</p>	<p>Slightly more than half of the respondents are aware of the nutrient value of the human excreta. The majority of the respondents think that human urine and faeces can be converted into safe fertilizer; however, most do not agree that human excreta should be used to fertilise the soil for edible crops. More than half were not willing to collect urine and faeces.</p>
<p>Andersson, 2015</p> <p>FPs: health risks/ fear of disease, taboo, odour, fear of the unknown, sociocultural norms, and stigmatisation/exclusion.</p> <p>SDP: human urine, human waste</p> <p>Acceptance: low, but if sociocultural norms are considered and incorporated into technology and reuse</p>	<p>To explore farmers' perceptions and evaluate the practice of the use of human urine as a crop fertilizer as a potential and partial solution to soil productivity problems.</p>	<p>Cultural issues and the paradoxes associated with the handling of human waste recurred in discussions with local farmers. It is typically a subject buried by avoidance, yet surrounded by numerous unwritten rules, norms and taboos. Many participants identified the distinctive smell of urine, 'fear of the unknown', health risks and fear of spreading disease (particularly associated with sexually transmitted diseases, including HIV/AIDS) as barriers, especially for leafy plants and vegetables that are eaten raw or unpeeled. The fear of exclusion and stigmatisation is a key barrier identified by farmers, as it is seen as a dirty thing.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Horlu, Egbadzor, Fafa, Afetorgbor, Akumah, 2024</p> <p>FPs: not indicated</p> <p>SDP: UDDT derived compost (Urine Diverting Dry Toilets)</p> <p>Acceptance: not clear</p>	<p>Examines farmers' adoption perception of human excreta compost from Urine Diversion Dry Toilets (UDDT) and to identify the linkages between various factors that could affect the adoption perception of the compost generated from UDDT facilities.</p>	<p>Mostly older respondents were willing to adopt the UDDT facility and use derived compost. Large households were more positively inclined to the UDDT facility and derived compost. The majority of the respondents have an interest in the adoption of the UDDT organic compost, irrespective of the factors considered. Possible barriers or perceptions were not indicated.</p>
<p>Lagerkvist, Shikuku, Okello, Karanja, and Ackello-Ogutu, 2015</p> <p>FPs: sociocultural factors; not identified</p> <p>SDP: human faeces</p> <p>Acceptance: not clear</p>	<p>To introduce attitude as behaviour approach to examine a farmers' attitudes to ISFM, in which behaviours are means to attitudinal ends, and present a case study investigating ISFM attitude-behaviour among commercial peri-urban farmers in a low-income country.</p>	<p>Many farmers in the sample have not come to adopted the majority of practices defined by the ISFM concept, including the use of human faeces. The difficulties related to the use of human faeces as fertiliser are most likely related to a cultural dimension, representing non-pecuniary aspects of behaviour.</p>
<p>Osei-Marfo, deVries and Awuah, 2021</p> <p>FPs: none</p> <p>SDP: biogas</p> <p>Acceptance: high</p>	<p>To assess the effect of people's perceptions on the use of human excreta for biogas generation in Ghana by exploring their opinions on the use of human excreta for biogas generation from religious, economic, educational and environmental points of view.</p>	<p>Most respondents reported strong knowledge of the benefits of biogas (e.g. alternative fuel for cooking, generating electricity, bio-fertiliser on farmlands, creating job opportunities, improving environmental sanitation and public health, and offering an environmentally friendly identity). Respondents reported positive perceptions towards the use of human excreta for biogas suggesting that the positive benefits of biogas, as expressed by the respondents, may influence their perceptions and decision to use it.</p>
<p>Ekane, Slovic, and Westlund, 2015</p> <p>Fps: risks, unsafe practices, untreated excreta</p> <p>SDP: human excreta</p> <p>Acceptance: high, depending on occupation</p>	<p>To explore the psychological mechanisms underlying perceptions and judgment of practices and technologies involving specifically the use of treated and untreated excreta as fertiliser in agriculture ("toilet to farm" systems).</p>	<p>Unsafe practices and technologies involving direct contact with excreta were judged high in risk and low in benefit, and conversely, safe practices and technologies involving treated excreta were judged high in benefit and low in risk, which is an indication of pathogen sensitivity. High sensitivity was indicated for fertilising leafy vegetables with untreated faeces, manual transportation of untreated faeces, application of faecal sludge to the farm, weeding farm fertilised with untreated faeces and urine. Fertilising non-fruit trees and flowers with human excreta was perceived as safe. Generally, practices such as fertilisation of leafy vegetables with untreated faeces and eating raw crops fertilised with human excreta are judged high in risks and low in benefits.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Uddin, Muhandiki, Sakai, Al Mamun, and Hridi, 2014</p> <p>FPs: sociocultural (not clear) SDP: UDDT (Urine Diverting Dry Toilets) Acceptance: high</p>	<p>To assess the socio-cultural acceptance and replication of UDDTs in rural Muslim communities in Bangladesh</p>	<p>UDDTs have been generally accepted by almost all users and, to some extent, by non-users. There were some social and cultural barriers to accepting UDDTs in the study area. Major drivers, which need to be further explored and researched, were found to heavily influence the acceptance and replication of UDDTs. The biggest challenge to the acceptance of this technology was not the replication of UDDTs or socio-cultural barriers, but high construction cost, dependence on subsidies from donors and a lack of financial contribution from the government.</p>
<p>Conroy and Mancini, 2022</p> <p>Fps: dangers, undesirable, unhygienic, impure, unnatural, perceived risk of disease, handling human waste, lack of training SDP: UDDT (Urine Diverting Dry Toilets) Acceptance: not indicated</p>	<p>To understand barriers and facilitators to the adoption of UDDTs from the adopters' /potential adopters' perspectives.</p>	<p>Human excreta reuse still appeared as a main facilitator and barrier to UDDT adoption. The main barrier was that handling human waste was seen as unacceptable. Contrary findings in another Ethiopian study found that concentrated waste from composting toilets was seen as dangerous and undesirable. Another study found that both adopter and non-adopters used hygiene, purity, and 'naturalness' as reasons for their contradictory decisions. An anticipated risk of disease when handling waste products and a lack of training on how to empty UDDTs were each noted as barriers.</p>
<p>Nimoh, Ohene-Yankyer, Poku, Konradsen, and Abaidoo, 2014</p> <p>FPs: health risks SDP: excreta, fertiliser Acceptance: high (if treated)</p>	<p>To investigate farmers' attitudes and perceptions towards excreta reuse for peri-urban agriculture in Sha-Osudoku District.</p>	<p>Most respondents were willing to use excreta as fertiliser or consume crops fertilised with excreta. However, they mostly agree that handling human excreta can pose a great health risk, and it should not even be handled at all. Most participants agree that crops fertilised with human excreta were good for consumption. Perception and attitude were dependent on socioeconomic characteristics.</p>
<p>Mamera, van, Tol, Aghoghovwia, and Mapetere, 2020</p> <p>Fps: perceived fear of disease (not the focus) SDP: treated faecal sludge, fertiliser, biochar Acceptance: high</p>	<p>To capture social perceptions regarding latrine sludge management and perceived water quality, as well as perceptions on treated faecal sludge use in agriculture.</p>	<p>Most participants in the study were willing to use treated faecal sludge in agriculture, but with some fear of disease, as well as adapting biochar use to reduce pit latrine baseline contaminant leaching.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Wilde Lieberherr, Pereira, Odindo, and Six, 2022.</p> <p>Fps: lack of knowledge and understanding not stated</p> <p>Barriers: SDP: urine, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: uncertain</p>	<p>To generate a joint understanding of the biophysical effectiveness of nitrified urine fertilisers, the challenges and opportunities facing smallholder producers in the case study of South African Swayimane, and farmer attitudes toward this novel fertiliser.</p>	<p>As a group, the farmers indicated that they would be willing to use NUF (Nitrified Urine Fertiliser) processed in Durban, but also voiced reservations about the process, indicating that because they could not envision the production process, they maintained scepticism toward the idea. They shared that there was little precedent for recycling human waste in their community and with little knowledge of its use, many farmers in the community would be reluctant to adopt, which would make it difficult to successfully scale up the technology as well as pose a risk to farmers trying to sell their produce if they became associated with the use of waste-based fertilizers, which would inhibit adoption.</p>
<p>Ejigu and Yeshtela, 2024</p> <p>Fps: sociocultural norms (not clear)</p> <p>SDP: human excreta, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: moderate</p>	<p>Assess the factors that influence urban farmers' intentions to adopt excreta-based organic fertilisers in Arba Minch city and identify the primary determinants influencing these intentions.</p>	<p>Farmers' attitudes and intentions towards the use of excreta-based organic fertilisers were significantly influenced by perceived behavioural control, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. A balanced perspective among urban farmers suggests neither strong favour nor disfavour toward the adoption of excreta-based organic fertiliser. Subjective norm would NOT favourably influence farmers' intentions. Perceived behavioural control (PBC) would positively influence farmers' intentions. The conflicting findings on the relationship between subjective norms on behavioural intention can be linked to several sociocultural elements and the unique environments in which farmers work.</p>
<p>Ajich, Isagba, Ihoeghian, Edosa, Amenaghawon, Oshoma, Erhummwunse, Obuekwe, Tongo, Emokaro, and Ezemonye, 2021</p> <p>Fps: lack of knowledge and awareness (not stated)</p> <p>SDP: biogas, faecal waste (fertiliser)</p> <p>Acceptance: moderate</p>	<p>Assess sociocultural and acceptability issues associated with the use of faecal waste as a source of energy .</p>	<p>Biogas generated from faecal waste is not socio-culturally acceptable, even though there is an indication for some use.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Gitau, Chumo, Muindi, Simiyu, and Mberu, 2020</p> <p>Fps: perceived health risks, religious beliefs, smell, sociocultural, lack of training</p> <p>SDP: faecal sludge, briquettes, fertiliser, biogas</p> <p>Acceptance: uncertain</p>	<p>Explore the attitudes towards the usage of recycled faecal sludge products.</p>	<p>Mixed attitudes towards various faecal sludge products (briquettes, fertiliser, and biogas). Some respondents voiced their reservations on using some products, like fertilisers, due to socio-cultural factors. The study also identified socio-cultural and religious factors that hinder community members from engaging in faecal waste management activities. Muslims regard any money associated with faecal sludge emptying and recycling as unclean, and they avoid being associated with such money. Some community members had fears over the safety of the products, expressing discomfort in using faecal sludge fertilisers on their crops, while others were open to their use.</p>
<p>Gwara, Wale, and Odindo, 2022a</p> <p>Fps: perceived health risks</p> <p>Barriers: perceived low behavioural control, perceived health risks, socio-cultural factors, norms, religion, and taboos</p> <p>SDP: human excreta, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: high</p>	<p>Scope and synthesise the stock of published research on the social acceptance of human excreta reuse in agriculture.</p>	<p>Social acceptance was driven by awareness, religiosity, income, source of income, and environmental dispositions. Perceived behavioural control represents a potential barrier to human excreta reuse. Environmental consciousness was positively related to willingness to recycle human excreta. Negative perceptions like perceived health risk and low self-efficacy, or self-evaluation of skills required to use human excreta potential, were indicated. Socio-cultural factors, norms, religion, and taboos were also found to be barriers to human excreta use; however, the farmers doubted if family members would eat food produced using human excreta, indicating a strong influence of subjective norms.</p>
<p>Okem, Xulu, Tilley, Buckley, and Roma, 2013</p> <p>Fps: Health concerns, smell, others' opinions, religion, magical reasons, lack of awareness, dangerous to plants, pollutes the soil, kills insects in gardens</p> <p>SDP: urine, fertiliser, UDDT (Urine Diverting Dry Toilet)</p> <p>Acceptance: very low</p>	<p>To assess the willingness to handle and use urine in agriculture among people living in rural areas of eThekweni Municipality.</p>	<p>This study explored UDDT users' perceptions of using urine in agricultural activities. Health concerns, smell, and others' opinions are barriers, as well as limited awareness of the value of urine in agriculture. Results show that close to half of the respondents think that urine kills plants and that urine pollutes the soil. More than half of the respondents agree to use fertiliser from the urine of family members; however, a few would use the urine of their neighbours.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Mkude, Gabriellson, and Kimwaga, 2021</p> <p>Fps: feelings of disgust, religious beliefs, taboo, perception of waste, lack of awareness</p> <p>SDP: urine and excreta-derived compost, proteins, biogas, briquettes</p> <p>Acceptance: low</p>	<p>To explore residents' views on faecal sludge resource recovery and reuse projects in Dar es Salaam.</p>	<p>The immediate emotional reactions from the participants upon seeing the displayed photos of the Faecal Sludge-derived products and accompanying oral descriptions were negative. These negative feelings could be explained by both limited knowledge and persisting cultural norms and taboos toward human waste. Those products that have direct or indirect links to human contact, ingestion or fear of foul smell score the lowest, because they trigger people's emotions of disgust and violate existing religious norms. These products are such as vegetables fertilised with urine, poultry fed from FS-derived proteins for animal or food cooked using biogas.</p>
<p>Roxburgh, Hampshire, Tilley, Oliver, and Quilliam, RS., 2020</p> <p>Fps: feelings of disgust, appearance, smell (Not clear)</p> <p>SDP: excreta, compost, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: high for dried granulated compost; low for the wet and lumpy option</p>	<p>To assess factors influencing the public acceptability of using human excreta-derived fertiliser in peri-urban agriculture for a range of locally grown crops.</p>	<p>Showing the composted, granulated faecal sludge sample to the participants evoked a more positive response compared to showing either the dried faecal sludge sample or no sample, depending on the product. Characteristics that had significant and consistent associations with not accepting human manure use were Yao (ethnicity) or Muslim. Having previously heard of HEDF also had a significant effect on participants. Maize was acceptable to be grown with HEDF, but leafy green vegetables were not, based on the degree of contact that the edible part of the crop was perceived to have with the ground. Maize was considered suitable, but not leafy green vegetables. Attitudes could be positive with previous knowledge.</p>
<p>Moya, Parker, Sakrabani, Sakrabani, and Mesa, 2019</p> <p>Fps: None, but fear of stigma and limited knowledge hinted</p> <p>SDP: human excreta, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: high (but questionable)</p>	<p>To analyse the quality of fertilisers produced from human excreta and evaluate their acceptability within the local market.</p>	<p>Positive attitudes of farmers indicated no local stigma associated with human-derived excreta fertiliser. The majority of farmers, however, stated they would not tell their customers about the origin of the fertilisers, showing that there is a fear of stigma of using faecal matter of human origin to produce the fertilisers. However, the acceptability of its use was not clear. Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were implied in acceptability.</p>
<p>Roma, Philip, Buckley, Xulu, and Scott, 2013b</p> <p>Fps: smell, disgust</p> <p>SDP: human urine, UDDT</p> <p>Acceptance: low</p>	<p>To explore the post-implementation challenges of urine diversion dehydration toilets (UDDTs) after a decade of installation and the adaptive processes necessary to increase the sustained use of the toilets.</p>	<p>Results report low levels of satisfaction with the UDDT facilities as well as perception of smell from the toilets.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Banamwana, Musoke, Niakirutimana, Buregyeya, Ssempebwa, Wamuyu-Maina, and Tumwesigye, 2023</p> <p>Fps: disgust, perceived health risks, stigma, harassment, taboos, contagion SDP: human excreta, fertiliser Acceptance: low</p>	<p>To explore perceptions of the use of Ecosan-by-products as it relates to the disgust of human excreta among rural farmers in Burera District.</p>	<p>Traditional excreta disgust and the perception of Ecosan products as contagious waste and health risk influenced willingness to reuse negatively. Some farmers expressed fear about fresh excreta, and such faecophobia extended the stigma, harassment, taboos, and manipulation of Ecosan by-products. Other participants were willing to use excreta derivatives such as urine and faeces when they are protected, indicating fear of exposure to contagion. Some farmers' mindsets of fear and stigma remained unchanged. The main constraint on willingness to use Ecosan by-products was health risks associated with the use of "contagious" products.</p>
<p>Gwara, Wale, Odindo, and Buckley, 2020</p> <p>Fps: health risks, fear of diseases, fear of awful smell, visual repulsiveness, handling, skin infections, socio-cultural factors, religion, taboos, and many other occupational hazards SDP: human excreta, fertiliser Acceptance: mixed (high in some and low in some studies)</p>	<p>To identify and synthesise published evidence on farmers' willingness to pay for human excreta-derived material for agricultural use.</p>	<p>Perceived health risk and socio-cultural factors were reported as the main barriers to the use of human excreta-derived materials in agriculture. Limited information, availability, collection, transport, and storage were the other reported perceived barriers. Most of the findings demonstrated positive attitudes and perceptions towards the use of human excreta and HEDM in agriculture. The use of fresh excreta was associated with bad smell, visual repulsiveness and various kinds of potential diseases, skin infections, handling and occupational hazards. Other perceived barriers included socio-cultural factors, religion, norms, and taboos. The inconclusive effect of socio-cultural factors (such as cultural norms, religion, beliefs, and taboos) and socioeconomic and demographic factors on perceptions could be due to the contextual differences of the studies.</p>
<p>Gwara, Wale, and Odindo, 2022b</p> <p>Fps: perceived health risks, religiosity, and environmental attitudes SDP: human excreta, co-compost, fertiliser Acceptance: uncertain</p>	<p>To understand the ecological worldviews of rural farming communities and implications for human excreta reuse in agriculture.</p>	<p>Rural farmers are moderately environmentally conscious. Pro-environmental farmers perceived lower health risk and believed they were more capable of using human excreta. The findings also indicate the influence of income, religiosity, and environmental attitudes on farmers' willingness to pay for co-compost. The results demonstrate the importance of addressing perceived and actual health risks through certification.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Williams, Quilliam, Campbell, Ghatani, and Dickie, 2022</p> <p>Fps: Socio-cultural resistance, and socio-technical factors SDP: urine, fertiliser Acceptance: varied depending on technicalities and personal motivations</p>	<p>To explore how socio-cultural resistance impacts Toilet-linked anaerobic digesters' adoption and subsequent use of biogas.</p>	<p>Although socio-cultural resistance was articulated as a challenge by some and does restrict the use of biogas, it does not prevent users from perceiving TLADs as beneficial overall. However, socio-cultural resistance is the most commonly reported barrier for TLAD adoption, yet findings from this study suggest there are more complex socio-technical factors influencing acceptance or resistance. Biogas use was based on socio-cultural norms as well as the quantity available; the slurry was used based on its performance, and where users were confident using it. The rate of acceptance of both biogas and slurry varied with technical performance and perceived motivations.</p>
<p>van den Broek, Nybom, Hartmann, Doetterl, and Garland, 2024</p> <p>Fps: disgust, health risk, risk of infection, sociocultural norms or religious beliefs SDP: human excreta, fertiliser Acceptance: uncertain</p>	<p>To investigate the suitability of reusing human excreta as fertiliser, ... and the social acceptance of these fertilisers.</p>	<p>Consumer acceptance of HEDFs is highly person-dependent and depends on country, HEDF type and plant type (i.e. edible and inedible). Consumers generally prefer the use of HEDFs for inedible plants such as ornamental flowers and plants. If consumers are not convinced of the use of HEDFs, it is likely because of the associated disgust and the perceived risk, but it can also be due to sociocultural norms or religious beliefs.</p>
<p>Nicholas, Halfacree, Mabbett, 2022</p> <p>Fps: feelings of disgust, revulsion, lack of knowledge SDP: faecal sludge biochar, biosolids, fertiliser Acceptance: biosolids-high, biochar-low</p>	<p>To collect information on public perceptions of exposure and risks towards consuming crops grown using faecal sludge biochar.</p>	<p>There is a need to overcome the "disgust effect" related to human faecal origins. The majority of respondents were generally okay with eating food grown with treated sewage sludge (biosolids), at least slightly comfortable, though a few were uncomfortable or very uncomfortable with it. There was greater reluctance to eat food grown in faecal sludge biochar, with over a quarter of respondents expressing clear discomfort, even if over a third were still very comfortable in doing so. Approximately a quarter identified a "disgust effect" for eating food grown with biochar. Notably, many of the statements regarding disgust focused on the very words "faecal sludge" and showed wider evidence of "squeamishness" or the "ick factor". Many also admitted that "they knew their attitude was not 'logical' or 'rational'". Perceptions and attitudes towards faecal sludge biochar significantly changed when more information regarding the safety of faecal sludge biochar was provided.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Simha, Barton, Perez-Mercado, McConville, Lalander, Magri, Dutta, Kabir, Selvakumar, Zhou, Martin, Kizos, Kataki, Gerchman, Herscu-Kluska, Alrousan, Goh, Elenciu, Glowacka, Korulanin, Tzeng, Ray Niwagaba, Prouty, Mihelcic, Vinnerås, 2021</p> <p>Fps: perceived health risk, social norms, perception of colleagues ' opinions SDP: human urine, fertiliser Acceptance: moderate (in some cases, very low)</p>	<p>Evaluate the behavioural intentions of food consumers across the world to recycle human urine, particularly as fertiliser for food crops and understand potential barriers to acceptance.</p>	<p>Overall, the majority of the respondents favoured recycling human urine, stated a willingness to eat urine-fertilised food, while only a few believed that urine posed health risks that could not be mitigated by treatment. Consumer perceptions differed greatly from country to country, from very low to high. Acceptance was influenced by perceptions of risks and benefits, and social norms. In general, more respondents found using urine as a crop fertiliser to be acceptable versus the use of it to water gardens/lawns or generate electricity. Overall, a little more than half were willing to eat food grown with human urine, indicating a moderate level of willingness. There was an indication of the willingness to consume food grown with human urine, and the perception of colleagues' opinions.</p>
<p>Gwara, Wale, Odindo, and Buckley, 2021</p> <p>Fps: perceived health risk, stigma, fear of exposure, and socio-cultural norms, bad smell, visual repulsiveness and various kinds of potential diseases, handling, skin infections, socio-cultural factors, religion, norms, taboos and occupational hazards SDP: human excreta, fertiliser Acceptance: high</p>	<p>Provide a scope of published literature on the influence of attitudes and perceptions on the intention to use human excreta and human excreta-derived materials in agriculture.</p>	<p>Attitudes and perceptions may vary depending on whether the crop is consumed, as this has implications for the contamination pathway and pathogen load in terms of microbial risk assessment. The reluctance of farmers to grow edible crops with HEDM or human excreta was due to perceived health risks resulting from perceived rejection by consumers. The health concerns included fear of awful smell, handling, skin infections, including others like socio-cultural factors, religion, taboos and many other occupational hazards. Lack of knowledge was also a potential barrier. Visual contact with human excreta was considered a reminder of one's internal badness and a taboo. Potential direct exposure to HEDM for leafy vegetables was another reason for poor acceptance for use on edible crops. Use of fresh excreta was associated with bad smell, visual repulsiveness and various kinds of potential diseases.</p>
<p>Eom, Oh, Cho, and Kim, 2021</p> <p>Fps: not stated (not focused) SDP: urine, fertiliser Acceptance: high</p>	<p>To investigate residents' social acceptance of smart Eco-toilets as an alternative to flushing toilets.</p>	<p>Residents and households indicated high social acceptance of the alternative Eco-toilet systems. The respondents who intend to use the Eco-toilet seemed to have different perceptions and attitudes toward human faeces, flush toilets, and bioenergy compared to those who wish to continue to use flush toilets.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Singh, Ibrahim, Pawar, and Brđjanović, 2022</p> <p>Fps: bad odour, feelings of disgust, fear of infection, religious and socio-cultural beliefs, stigma, and inadequate information</p> <p>SDP: human excreta, co-compost</p> <p>Acceptance: high</p>	<p>To investigate people's perceptions of faecal sludge co-compost, identify factors influencing negative perceptions, and explore people's willingness to consume food crops produced using faecal sludge co-compost</p>	<p>Main perceptions were influenced by feelings of disgust, fear of infection, bad odour, religious and socio-cultural beliefs. And inadequate information. FPOs perceived that their members would use FS co-compost, but there might be some stigma for early adopters. They perceived FS co-compost reuse in agriculture to be acceptable, and were willing to use it if it was safe to use, readily available, and accessible, and if it increased crop yield. Only a few of the respondents on all fronts were willing to eat food grown with FS co-compost due to the fear of infection. Also majority of the farmers were unwilling to disclose to their customers their usage of FS co-compost to fertilise food crops to avoid being stigmatised.</p>
<p>Khalid, 2018</p> <p>Fps: health risks, disgust, feelings of disgust, religious beliefs, socio-cultural factors, unhygienic, impure, dirt, risk of infection, stigma</p> <p>SDP: human excreta, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: low</p>	<p>To understand the perceptions of people about the reuse of human excreta for agricultural purposes.</p>	<p>The community majorly rejected the idea of human waste composting because they were apprehensive about the reuse of human excreta. They used the term najasat (dirt) and said that Allah has given Muslims paki (purity) so how can they reuse their excretion? In their opinion, excreta handling is unhygienic and would damage health. But, preference was for annual crops like maize, wheat, barley, etc, but not for directly consumed crops like vegetables. People became more favourable when excreta changes its composition, colour and odour. However, social and cultural taboos attached to the reuse of human excreta cannot be undermined, especially concerning social class segregation, as only lower classes or cleaners are associated with handling, managing and reusing of human excreta.</p>
<p>Simha, Lalander, Ramanathan, Vijayalakshmi, McConville, Vinnerås, and Ganesapillai, 2018</p> <p>Fps: health risk, sociocultural, stigma, Fear of crop die-off, fear of being ridiculed, and uncertainty</p> <p>SDP: faeces, urine, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: moderate</p>	<p>To identify and analyse the factors that encourage or discourage, negative and positive attitudes to human waste recycling among farmers in Vellore District.</p>	<p>A moderately positive attitude was observed. Most of them agreed that urine should be recycled rather than disposed of. Above average considered it as a fertiliser. Less than average would consume food grown using human urine-based fertiliser. Although a high number feared the perceived health risks, the majority were confident that treatment does not pose a risk. Fear of crop die-off, fear of being ridiculed and uncertainty over consumer marketplace behaviour were significant factors among farmers with a negative attitude.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Müller, Pedro, and de Castro Freitas, 2017</p> <p>FPs: religion, culture, negative effect on soil, lack of knowledge</p> <p>SDP: urine, fertiliser, UDDTs</p> <p>Acceptance: medium</p>	<p>To evaluate farmers' perceptions of the use of human urine as a fertiliser for crops in Central Amazon.</p>	<p>More than a third of the farmers thought it was possible to use urine in their gardens and fields. More than half would not consider using urine as they were not convinced of its efficacy. Some perceived that urine-grown crops were good for consumption. Perception varied according to cultural norms. Farmers who would not use urine primarily expressed concerns regarding crop development as well as doubts related to the efficacy of urine as a fertiliser.</p>
<p>Buit, and Jansen, 2016</p> <p>Fps: faeces as cultural, moral, or religious badness, disgust, health risk, appearance, smell, health risk, stigma, religion, lack of knowledge and understanding</p> <p>SDP: human faeces, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: varied (depending on treatment)</p>	<p>To examine perceptions of both human faeces and fertilisers based on their among fertiliser users around Accra.</p>	<p>Fresh human faeces is intimidating and induces negative perceptions. Dried and treated faeces are no longer visually intimidating, and their use as a fertiliser is generally considered acceptable. Very diverse levels of and reasons for acceptance of human faeces-based fertilisers. Some find the idea of using human faeces so disgusting that they say they will never consider it. Fear of customer avoidance is often an important consideration; respondents did not indicate a reason for accepting or not accepting faeces-based fertilisers. Physical appearance also affected acceptance: fresh faeces are generally considered disgusting and unfit for use as fertilisers, while dried or treated faeces are more acceptable. Some respondents indicated that they simply copy neighbours' behaviour when choosing fertilisers because they fear unacceptance by their social environment.</p>
<p>McConville, Metson, and Persson, 2023</p> <p>FPs: health risk, taste, quality, disgust, environmental impact, origin</p> <p>SDP: human urine, fertiliser</p> <p>Acceptance: low</p>	<p>To assess the acceptability of human excreta-derived fertilisers as a way to gauge the readiness of Swedish food retailers to promote nutrient recycling as part of a sustainable food system.</p>	<p>More specifically, respondents thought struvite was less harmful to the environment than urine, while struvite and ash were less harmful to their health than urine. Respondents were more accepting of human-derived fertilisers not for human consumption. They were significantly positive about using struvite or dehydrated urine on inedible plants and animal feed than for human consumption. The same was the case for willingness to eat food grown with any given product. Potential problems with medicinal/pharmaceutical residues and antibiotic resistance were also worrisome, along with the spreading of diseases. Lack of knowledge combined with safety concerns also seems to make respondents less willing to consider nutrient reuse.</p>

Author(s) & Publication Date	Study Objectives	Main Findings
<p>Sugihara, 2020</p> <p>FPs: crop quality, risk of infections, stigma SDP: human excreta, fertiliser Acceptance: varied</p>	<p>No clear objective</p>	<p>Even though the use of human excreta has positive effects on soils, public perception of excreta is critical. Some farmers suspect composting could spread infections; they assume that consumers would avoid crops on which co-compost had been used for fear of infections.</p>
<p>Roma, Benoit, Buckley, and Bell, 2013a</p> <p>FPs: religious beliefs, health risks, sociocultural norms, disgust, smell, taste SDP: human urine, fertiliser Acceptance: low</p>	<p>To highlight opportunities for achieving a sustained use of “alternative” sanitation systems by discussing human barriers to acceptance and use of urine through the lenses of the Receptivity conceptual framework.</p>	<p>Particularly, cultural and religious beliefs as well as health concerns represented a barrier to the re-use of urine. Conversely, sensorial perceptions (smell, and taste) played an important role in acceptance of urine as fertiliser, associated with feelings of disgust, as many worried that crops smell and taste like urine and the feeling of disgust towards urine has led some farmers to conceal the use of urine for agricultural activities to retain customers. Also, public perceptions of health risks and ecotoxicological effects associated with using urine as fertiliser in crops, depending on the crop, have higher acceptance of urine when applied to non-comestible plants. There were concerns about the presence of micro-pollutants, hormones, pathogens, pharmaceutical residues and other contaminants in urine, as well as the risk of the spread of HIV/AIDS. Social stigma is attached to using dry sanitation and reusing urine in agriculture.</p>

Figure 10: Number of publications by Types of Faecophobic Perceptions identified

4.3 Influence of Faecophobic Perceptions (FPs) on the acceptance of Sanitation-Derived-Products (SDPs) reuse

For most of the studies that identified FPs as reactions to SDPs' reuse, they indicated these perceptions influenced the acceptance of SDPs to some extent by acting as barriers (Figure 11). 19 studies identified the fear of stigmatisation and the opinions of others as the major perception influence, mainly with buyers of crops, neighbours and family as affecting SDPs acceptance, whether positive or negative. For example, the fear of stigmatisation could make people refuse to accept SDPs and related technologies to avoid exclusion (Andersson 2015, Ejigu and Yeshitela, 2024, Gitau et al 2020, Okem et al 2013, Moya et al, 2019, Banamwana et al, 2023, Gwara et al 2020, van den Broek et al 2024, Simha et al, 2021, Singh et al, 2022, Simha 2018, Buit and Jansen, 2016), and the fear of what neighbours might think or the rejection of crops grown with SDPs by customers greatly influenced acceptance (Khalid 2018, Simha et al 2018, 2020, Ignacio et al 2018).

Meanwhile, a total of 16 papers concluded that FPs influence perceived health risks barrier out of fear of infection, disease, crop contamination, soil pollution, smell and taste of excreta in crops (especially leafy vegetables, roots, and tubers), and health concerns from pathogen transmission, and pharmaceuticals and micro-pollutants transmission and even disease transmission such as HIV and other related diseases (van den Broek et al, 2024, McConville et al 2023, Gwara et al, 2022, 2021, 2020, Singhet al, 2022, Mamera et al, 2020, Ignacio et al, 2018, Andersson 2015, Nimoh et al 2014, Roma et al 2013a, Okem et al, 2013).

Figure 11: Number of publications by Types of Perception Barriers to SDP Acceptance identified

The next way that FPs were implied to influence acceptance of SDPs' reuse, according to 12 studies, was due to a lack of knowledge, awareness and education that arises from fear of the unknown/uncertainties and unsafe practices/untreated excreta in the usage. In addition, the FPs could also influence acceptance by activating behaviour related to excreta disgust (19 studies) and sensory avoidance (12 studies) that create barrier to accepting reuse of SDPs (Ejigu and Yeshitela 2024, van den Broek, 2024, Gwara et al 2022, 2021a,b, 2020, Banamwana et al, 2023, Williams et al 2022, Singh et al, 2022, Gitau et al 2020, Mkude e al 2021, Simha et al 2021, Khalid 2018, Muller et al 2017, Mugivhisa and Olowoyo 2015, Built and Jansen 2016). Other barriers influenced by FPs include sociocultural factors such as religion (Gwara et al 2022, van den Broek, 2024, Singh et al, 2022, Gitau et al, 2020), taboos (Gwara et al 2022, 2020, Banamwana et al 2023, Okem and Odindo, 2020, Ignacio et al 2018, Mugivhisa and Olowoyo, 2015, Okem et al 2013), witchcraft/magic (Ignacio et al 2018, Okem et al 2013, Gwara et al 2022), and other social norms that involve relationship considerations. In some SSA communities, for instance, a woman is not allowed to share toilets with her father-in-law or have anything to do with his human waste as this implies intimacy (van den Broek 2024, Banamwana et al, 2023, Gwara et al, 2021). Religion further creates a barrier in the doctrines on handling human waste like in Christianity, Judaism, Islam, Hindu and Buddhism (Khalid et al, 2018, Roxburgh et al 2020, Gitau et al, 2020, Simha et al, 2018); in fact, Muslims generally regard any money human excreta emptying and recycling as unclean and would prefer not to be associated with such money (Roxburgh et al 2020).

Meanwhile, there is the fear of people's excreta being used for witchcraft and magical purposes with evil intents (Ignacio et al, 2018; Okem et al, 2013). Some papers also identified the refusal to handle excreta with excreta disgust and perceived contamination, risks of contact and infection and indicate that they influence unacceptance of SDPs' reuse; while perceived behavioural control (PBC) and environmental dispositions (Ejigu and Yeshitela, 2024, Gwara et al, 2022, Conroy and Mancini, 2022, McConville et al, 2023) also affect acceptance of the reuse of SDPs depending on the individual's perception of their ability to safely handle and use human excreta and urine (as well as related products) and environmental consciousness and desirability to protect the environment. Some of these issues appear together in a single

article more than once. These barriers influenced the willingness to buy and use these SDPs used in agriculture as well as consume crops grown and cooked with human-excreta-derived products (Singh et al, 2022; Mamera et al, 2020; Moya et al, 2019; Simha et al, 2021; Okem et al, 2013; Eom et al, 2021; Gwara et al, 2020).

Acceptance levels of SDPs' reuse were also gleaned from the studies in this review to find out how the publications rated it in their studies. Several of the studies were not clear about the acceptance levels; however, Figure 12 illustrates that the highest number of publications (that is, 15 studies) indicated that acceptance was high. However, considering that 11 studies found acceptance to be low, and 1 showed very low, while 7 indicated moderate levels of acceptance, it gives an impression of not-so-high acceptance, especially when up to 12 studies were either mixed/varied or uncertain. This implies that much work still needs to be done on improving the acceptance of SDPs' reuse. However, most of these studies were more focused on testing models and giving the results of those tests, and so were not exactly clear or focused on the perceptions identified and the responses.

Figure 12: Number of publications by levels of SDP Reuse Acceptance identified

4.4 Limitations from the studies

Generally, FPs were not identified, defined or described, even though faecophobia was indicated and perceptions were the focus of most of these papers. Most articles with perceptions in their titles did not define perception or what perceptions they referred to, and how these perceptions related to their subject matter. Many did not define or describe the SDPs or HEDPs under study enough, probably assuming that readers are fully knowledgeable. Most studies focused on farmers, while the regular residents who will use or consume these products were not adequately explored. It is still not clear what, how and how FPs affect intentions to reuse SDPs and subsequent behaviours towards HEDPs and resource/technology.

5.0 Discussion

It is obvious from this study that there is growing interest in perceptions that could be related to faecophobia, and how these perceptions could create barriers to acceptance of and willingness to interact with byproducts of human excreta and urine. Nevertheless, the results are discouragingly inconclusive on whether these FPs influence acceptance or not, as

even in some studies where they exist, willingness to use was still relatively high in some aspects, like the type of crops or type of SDP (whether treated or presented in a neutral form). It is also not clear how to manage these perceptions when they affect the way people choose to interact with SDPs. Some of the studies noted that there were people who indicated that they could change their minds about not accepting the SDP if they were provided with more information, but they didn't show whether the disgust, fear and aversion factor would be ameliorated by more information and/or training.

Even though about 34% of the studies reviewed indicated that acceptance of the SDP was high, which was more for urine than excreta, (in converted form) and biogas, the fact that the other studies recorded either low, very low or moderate levels, and about 12 studies had uncertain or mixed/varied acceptance levels shows that SDPs' acceptance are still questionable and this may affect a sanitation economy that depends on the bio-recirculation of nutrients and resources derived from human excreta and urine.

For many of the papers, perceptions were indicated as a focus, but they failed to define or describe what perception is being referred to in their study and how it would be reflected upon. To understand how perception affects behaviour and decisions, it is key to understand the source of such perceptions and the links to behaviour, whether positive or negative. Perception is the psychological process by which people make sense of the environment around them through the interpretation and organisation of sensory information (vision, hearing, smell, taste and touch) and cognitive abilities (such as attention, memory, and reasoning). It is subjective and influenced by past experiences, beliefs, values, emotions, expectations, culture and social context (Goldstein 2014). It shapes our attitudes and beliefs, which in turn guide our intentions. For example, if someone believes that a particular behaviour or decision will be beneficial, they are more likely to adopt it, and the reverse case also holds (Aditya, 2020; Savadori and Lauriola, 2020; Wijekoon, 2024). Individual perceptions shapes how a person views the world and guides behaviour and decisions while social perception guides the way people interpret and understand the behaviour, intentions and characteristics of others in social interactions (Fiske and Taylor, 2017), and how they respond (like in cases of fear of exclusion and stigma in society). Thus, to do a study on the perceptions linked to faecophobia and how it affects acceptance behaviour as it regards SDP reuse requires deeper exploration of these perceptions than was considered in these studies.

Costell et al (2010) in their study on the role of consumer perception and attitudes towards food acceptance, they noted that perceptions obtained from four categorical sources influence response: (a) observation, handling and consumption, (b) surrounding social and cultural contexts, (c) physiological effects (pleasure, dislike, discomfort, et), and (d) memory of past experiences. It is, therefore, important to note that acceptance of SDPs and the byproducts, such as food grown with human-derived excreta, will be dependent on perceptions drawn from these same sources. Studies have shown that the way consumers perceived a new product, service or technology will determine willingness to use or interact with the new introduction (Davis 1991, Albertsen et al, 2020, Pishnyak and Khalina 2021); much like perceptions have hindered the adoption of excreta related products in these studies and others before the timeline of this review (Duncker et al 2006, Duncker and Matsebe 2008, Drangert et al 2008, Danso, 2006). Ferguson (2004) shows, through several studies, that perception does not only affect behaviour, judgement, and decisions, but it can do so automatically without consciousness or prior thought; just like when Nicholas et al, (2022) and McConville et al, (2022) indicated that the participants in their studies admitted disgust at the thought of excreta derived products but had no explanation for their reactions. It seems then that studying the influence of perceptions on acceptance behaviour in the reuse of SDPs may require more than an understanding of Planned Behaviour, which is the preferred theoretical background for most of the studies reviewed.

In addition, there was no clear attempt to understand the faecophobia exhibited in most of the studies and how it feeds the anti-SDPs perceptions or even when it did not yield negative responses. Faecophobia is a concept that is often used to refer to the in-depth negative reactions to human excreta, whether one's own or that of others. It is different from coprophobia which is an abnormal and persistent fear of one's faeces that causes anxiety and avoidance behaviour (that could result in refusal to expels anally) and is often associated with Obsessive Compulsive Disorders (OCD) (Didensen, 2024). However, defined by Jenkins (1999) as the revulsion or anxiety experienced by most people when disposing of or managing their faeces. In the field of sanitation as it regards the reuse of human excreta and urine, it has been defined as a personal or cultural response or reaction to the fact that human faeces are 'malodorous and potentially dangerous' (Winblad and Simpson-Herbert, 2004; Esrey et al, 1998). Drangert and Mariwah (1998a,b) used the term 'urine blindness' to refer to the negative attitudes adopted towards the use of human urine as fertilisers in agriculture, whilst Esrey et al (1998) used faecophobia to describe the socio-cultural version of the Muslim community in their study of faeces.

Subsequently, faecophobia has become a term used to generally describe the socio-cultural reactions that connote strong resistance to any interaction with faeces. It has to do with the fear, disgust, and aversion towards faeces (whether excreta and/or urine), which leads to avoidance. Fear is often related to health risks such as disease transmission, contamination, pharmaceutical residues, crop and soil pollution, among others. It also includes fear of stigma and the opinions of others -- in the community and family. On the other hand, the disgust factor is related to the innate psychological reaction that stems from a preventive mechanism to self-protect against disease (Curtis et al, 2011; Rozin et al, 2015). It has to do with reactions to smell, appearance, (sight), taste, and touch (handle), and the irrational and illogical response to just the concept or thought of human waste in its regular usage (e.g. excreta, faeces, urine, shit, etc) (McConville et al, 2022). Then, there is aversion, which is related to a total disregard for handling or interacting with excreta in any shape or form, especially that of other people. However, Buit and Jansen (2016) restricted their conceptualisation of faecophobia (faecophoby) to the fear of physical health risks alone in their argument that Ghana was not exactly faecophobic, but then mentioned that other factors like 'disgust' were evident, which they assumed negated the label of faecophobia on Ghanaian societies.

Meanwhile, most of these papers described perceptions that related to these faecophobic tendencies without really relating them to faecophobia -- and only about five of the 39 studies referred to faecophobia. Thus, the concept of faecophobia is not yet clear in studies, even if it is in common usage, and so really needs to be clearly defined. This will enable more in-depth studies to be carried out to explore how faecophobic perceptions affect the way societies and individuals accept or reject SDPs' reuse, which will in turn contribute to interventions and marketing strategies to support the sanitation (bio)economy (Simha et al, 2018). However, a good number of the publications did not adequately define or describe what SDPs are (or the synonymous terms such as human-derived-excreta-products, human-derived-excreta-materials, faecal sludge derived, etc) even though they identified generic products and what they were used for such as compost, nitrified urine for fertiliser and extracted nutrients for biogas.

However, there were very few extensive explanations, and none of them used the term sanitation-derived products (SDP). Koottatep et al (2019) introduced the term sanitation-derived-products (SDPs) in their book, *Regenerative Sanitation: A New Paradigm for Sanitation 4.0*. They highlighted what they called the Sanitation Service Chain- Raw Materials (SSc-RaMs), which identified sanitation input materials such as faeces, urine, flushwater, greywater, anal cleansing water and dry materials, sludge (faeces/sewage), and other materials as Raw materials for the production of SDPs. This movement along the SSC represents how biomass from sanitation systems transform into reusable SDPs/byproducts and represents a shift from 'treatment and disposal' to 'cradle-to-cradle' (Masi et al, 2011, Braungart et al,

2007, Hodges, 2006).

These SDPs, they noted, are high on the development agenda as sustainability requires that essential resources are kept in circulation and put to productive use at every stage (Otoo and Drechsel, 2017; Andersson et al, 2016). Thus, Koottatep et al (2019) view SDPs will providing recoverable and reusable products such as treated used water, sanitation-derived fertilisers (SDFs), bioenergy, soil conditioners, and other materials (e.g. protein feed, building materials, trace elements, etc). These SDPs ensure that essential materials are delivered to target potential direct and indirect users and customers (like farmers and consumers of their crops grown with SDFs) for utilisation. This implies that tapping into the customer segment interested in the recovery of resources from sanitation materials for SDPs could provide an additional revenue stream through sales of SDPs and their byproducts, which could support the financial flow and offset disposal and treatment costs in a sanitation economy. The key highlight in this book is the potential to contribute to food security, energy security, urban regeneration, water security, and even the local economy. However, the focus of most studies has been on the human excreta and urine-derived products and their contribution to food and energy security, which greatly supports key SDGs like 6, 2, 3, 7, 8, 11, 12 and 13, showing the interconnections between SDG 6 and other SDGs. The SDPs in focus in this review paper are those directly sourced from human excreta and urine, and the other byproducts acquired therefrom. The book also highlighted the need for standardised treatment, production, and use of SDPs to ensure health and safety precautions as a means to support the market and value chain system for SDPs. Every study must make it clear which SDP is the focus, the treatment, safety, and standards, where available, that are adopted.

Lack of knowledge about the benefits of SDPs and education/training on their safe reuse was also a resulting barrier in most of the studies, as the fear of the unknown contact/exposure and of handling excreta without being sure of how to do it rightly and what potential results could accrue was a high concern. Thus, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness were considered leading factors to willingness to use the products, whether for agriculture or cooking. In addition, willingness to use, buy and consume (as per interactions with SDPs) was high for indirect contact and crops that have no direct or close contact with the soil or fertiliser. Ornamental crops like flowers and inedible plants were considered to be highly acceptable, while maize and corn were preferred over leafy vegetables (e.g. spinach, etc) and roots and tubers (e.g. yams, potato, carrots, etc) as well as other edibles. Even when cooking with biogas was acceptable, it was not used for religious cooking in societies like the Hindus (Simha et al., 2018).

One major point to note in this review is that the focus of most papers was on agriculture and farmers (or home gardeners), and in very few cases, domestic cooking, and in just one each bioenergy and latrine treatment. Other uses of SDP, such as building materials, horticulture, aquaculture and even industrial processes (Koottatep et al, 2019) should also be addressed to explore the effect of FPs on the reuse of these SDPs and how it could affect their market demand and prospective sanitation economy. Furthermore, studies should extend to non-agricultural users as well as to the general residents/citizens of a society or region who cut across the consumer/customer spectrum.

This review further shows that FPs are person and context specific and drawn from religion, socio-cultural norms and expectations, past experiences and even irrational psychological reactions like disgust. Thus, any study to comprehend what FPs are prevalent and how they affect acceptance of any SDP reuse, as well as the impacts on the marketplace and sanitation economy, should adequately address issues from these perspectives. In essence, studies should not just be about testing models or theories, but should go beyond to seek to glean usable and relevant information about the real perceptions of the people and how these FPs make them respond to the phenomenon. This will require mixed methods studies that inculcate percent ion theories and adaptations, and not just behaviour theories (which could amount to putting the cart before the horse). Conclusively, reports must be written in simple and clear language so policymakers,

practitioners, marketers, and implementers of related projects can easily use and refer to the knowledge therein.

5.1 Limitations of the study

This study was unable to access some of the richest databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, PsychInfo, and Science Direct due to the university institution not being subscribed to them (related to the high costs for a developing country university). Thus, some studies may have escaped scrutiny, especially since several studies were excluded because the researchers could only access abstracts and so could not glean adequate information from them. However, the researchers attempted to address this issue by harvesting papers from the reference section of available publications and contacting authors via ResearchGate to get full texts where possible. Furthermore, the analyses were all done manually as there was no access to relevant software such as NVivo to carry out thematic analysis, among others, and the time was short for such a laborious assignment. Nevertheless, this does not affect the quality of the findings herein as the researchers put in every effort to get as much information, data, and knowledge from in-depth studies of each of the papers reviewed in an iterative manner and with the use of a data extraction matrix.

5.2 Implications of the study

The study synthesis accrued from the integrative review points to an unclear conceptualisation of faecophobia and related perceptions, and how they influence the acceptance of sanitation-derived products and byproducts, including technologies like UDDTs, TLADs, ETS, and SETS. There is a need for perception studies in sanitation to be more reflective on the unique way that thoughts influence sanitation behaviour. For example, Cookey et al (2020) investigated how individual and social perceptions influence sanitation emptying behaviour, and how understanding this relationship could make behaviour change strategies more effective. They anchored their study on the linkages between perception and behaviour in that perceptions act as a trigger to behave correspondingly (Bargh and Ferguson 2000, Dijksterhuis and Knippenberg, 1998). They postulated that identifying the perceptions of onsite/non-sewer sanitation system users and empties could provide insights into understanding and predicting households and emptying workers' behaviour based on the assumption that perception of certain actions could lead to performance of such actions (Bargh and Ferguson 2000, Albarracin and Wyer, 2000, Ajzen 1985) or non-performance as the case may be (Jenkins et al, 2015). They, then, proposed emptying perceptions and perceptual cues (to suggest the stimuli that trigger actual perceptions creating the attitude and intentions to eventually perform the behaviour -- to empty), noting that perception and aligning cues potentially influence the development of sanitation-related behaviour based on what is perceived as influenced by the cues. Subsequently, they developed four constructs of non-sewer/onsite sanitation systems emptying perception-behaviour determinants derived from the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen 1985) and the RANAS model (Mosler 2012) and 6 perception cues. Perception-Behaviour Determinants were (i) perception of risks/hazards of emptying, (ii) perception of desired emptying behaviour, (iii) perception of emptying norms, and (iv) perception of emptying ability; while perception cues included (i) past emptying behaviour, (ii) sanitation beliefs system, (iii) consequences of previous emptying experiences, (iv) sanitation norms, (v) sanitation situational factors, and (vi) confidence in ability to empty effectively. Two perception strengtheners were also identified: information and cognitive processes (Cookey et al, 2020).

They were able to propose a change management model for understanding emptying perceptions and moving towards desired change levels (Cookey et al, 2020) to prove that perception change management is essential for sanitation behaviour change. This study shows how perception studies for understanding how FPs influence SDPs' reuse acceptance can be used to come up with intervention strategies to predict and redirect sanitation behaviour for desired change. It is, therefore, imperative that future research on FPs and SDPs' acceptance, especially as it affects the sanitation (bio)economy should strongly consider a mixed methods research with a direct focus on perceptions using perception and behaviour theories and models to produce workable and potentially effective interventions, policies, and market

strategies. This is a key contribution of this study towards future research.

This study has also highlighted the need for proper and clear training and knowledge dissemination aimed at perceptual change against FPs, especially as it regards perceived ease of use and usefulness, as well as the treatment and safety of SDPs' reuse. In addition, the appearance of SDPs has been shown to affect perceptions and change aspects, as shown by some studies (Roxburgh et al, 2020). Thus, it will be an effective measure to promote awareness creation and training interventions that explain the SDPs and byproducts before introducing reuse (Gwara et al, 2021), and also to consider product appearance and presentation in the marketplace. Furthermore, there is a need to provide an adaptable, non-prescriptive change model for FPs and managing their influence on acceptance behaviour and willingness to use, buy and consume by extension. Finally, considering that perceptions are person and context specific, each SSA country should consider policies that reflect and support a sanitation (bio)economy to encourage interactions with SDPs and their byproducts; and introduce regulations and standards for treatment, safety and reuse, which are crucial for ensuring confidence and trust in the system and personal abilities as well as in business investments. Studies are required in this area, too.

6.0 Conclusion

This review attempted to provide a synthesised knowledge on the extent of published research evidence available from 2013 - 2025. This was the first time that a review explored how FPs influence the acceptance of SDPs' reuse in SSA with the aid of a mixed review method: descriptive, exploratory, and integrative. It was observed that perception models were not used in any of the studies, which may have affected the design and results of the reviewed publications. It was also observed that faecophobia and perception were not properly defined or described, even though they were referred to in most of the papers. This is also the first time that faecophobic perceptions (FPs) are categorically identified and described in literature. Specifically, this review paper highlights the need for a perception change, deeper insights into the relationship between FPs and acceptance of SDPs' reuse, and for change interventions in this regard towards improving acceptance, market demands, and a sanitation (bio)economy in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Effective policies targeting faecophobic perceptions can accelerate the acceptance of human-derived excreta products in Sub-Saharan Africa. By addressing cultural, financial, and regulatory barriers, policymakers can unlock the potential of these products to enhance sanitation, agricultural productivity, and environmental sustainability. Collaborative efforts among governments, communities, and international organisations are key to achieving widespread adoption.

References

- Abdulhalim, M. A., Ahmed, A., Moges, A. M., Nayem, Z., Minza, I. S., Muhammad, A. A., & Rohaeni, E. S. (2023). Fecal Sludge Recycling to Useful Products: Environmental Concerns, Viability and Potential. *Applied Research and Innovation*, 1(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ari.v1i1.1526>
- Agrawal, R., Agrawal, S., Samadhiya, A., Kumar, A., Luthra, S., and Jain, V., 2024. Adoption of green finance and green innovation for achieving circularity: An exploratory review and future directions. *Geoscience Frontiers*, Vol.: 4, pp. 101669. ISSN 1674-9871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsf.2023.101669>
- Ahmed, K and Ahmed, SS., 2017. Socio-cultural acceptability of urine diverted composting toilets: A review of literature for possible adoption in peri-urban areas as a sustainable sanitation solution. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 28 December 2017; 1919 (1): 020043. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5018561>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Ajeh, M.U., Isagba, E.S., Ihoeghian, Edosa, VI., Amenaghawon, A., Oshoma, CE., Erhunmwunse, N., Obuekwe, IS., Tongo, I., Emokaro, C., and Ezemonye, LIN., 2021. Assessment of sociocultural acceptability of biogas from faecal

- waste as an alternative energy source in selected areas of Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. *Environ Dev Sustain* 23, 13182–13199. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-020-01205-y>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Akpan VE, Omole DO, Bassey DE. Assessing the public perceptions of treated wastewater reuse: opportunities and implications for urban communities in developing countries. *Heliyon*. 2020 Oct;6(10):e05246. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05246. Epub 2020 Oct 14. PMID: 33072925; PMCID: PMC7556266. Accessed: 10 December 2024
- Albertsen, L., Wiedmann, K., and Schmidt, S., 2020. The impact of innovation-related perception on consumer acceptance of food innovations – Development of an integrated framework of the consumer acceptance process. *Food Quality and Preference*, Vol. 84:103958. ISSN 0950-3293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2020.103958>
- Andersson, E., 2015. Turning waste into value: using human urine to enrich soils for sustainable food production in Uganda. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol 96, pp 290-298. ISSN 0959-6526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.01.070>
- Appiah-Effah, E., Nyarko, K. B., Adum, L., Antwi, E. O., & Awuah, E. (2015). Perception of Peri-Urban Farmers on Fecal Sludge Compost and Its Utilization: A Case Study of Three Peri-Urban Communities in Ashanti Region of Ghana. *Compost Science & Utilization*, 23(4), 267–275. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1065657X.2015.1046616>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Badza, T.; Musazura, W.; Shoji, M. Z.; Odindo, A. O.; Mabhaudhi, Tafadzwanashe. 2024. Progress towards the circular economy: case studies of sanitation and organic waste-derived resource recovery technologies in South Africa. In Nhamo, L.; Mpandeli, S.; Liphadzi, S.; Mabhaudhi, Tafadzwanashe. (Eds.). *Circular and transformative economy: advances towards sustainable socio-economic transformation*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press. pp.101-138. (Africa Circular Economy Series)
- Baghapour, MA., Shoosharian, MR., and Djahed, B 2017. A survey of attitudes and acceptance of wastewater reuse in Iran: Shiraz City as a case study. *Journal of Water Reuse and Desalination* 1 December 2017; 7 (4): 511–519. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2166/wrd.2016.117>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Banamwana, C., Musoke, D., Ntakirutimana, T., Buregyeya, E., Ssempebwa, J., Wamuyu-Maina, G., & Tumwesigye, N. M. 2023. Excreta Disgust and Adaptive Use of Ecological Sanitation By-Products: Perspectives of Rural Farmers in Burera District, Rwanda. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(18), 6743. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20186743>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Barton, MA., Simha, P., Magri, ME., Dutta, S., Kabir, H., Selvakumar, A., Zhou, X., Lv, Y., Martin, T., Kizos, T., Triantafyllou, E., Katakaki, R., Gerchman, Y., Herscu-Kluska, R., Alrousan, D., Dalahmeh, S., Goh, GH., Elenciu, D., Głowacka, A., Korculanin, L., Tzeng, RV., Ray, SS., Ganesapillai, M., Niwagaba, C., Prouty, C., Mihelcic, JR., Vinnerås, B., 2021. Attitudes of food consumers at universities towards recycling human urine as crop fertiliser: A multinational survey dataset. *Data in Brief*, Vol 35:06794. ISSN 2352-3409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2021.106794>. Accessed: 10 December 2024
- Buit, G., and Jansen, K., 2016. Acceptance of Human Feces-based Fertilizers in Fecophobic Ghana. *Human Organization* 75 (1): 97–107. doi: <https://doi.org/10.17730/0018-7259-75.1.97>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Cataldo, I., Banaitis, A., Samadhiya, A., Banaitienė, N., Kumar, A, and Luthra, S., 2022. Sustainable supply chain management in construction: an exploratory review for future research. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Management*, Vol. 28:7: 536–553. ISSN 1392-3730/eISSN 1822-3605. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jcem.2022.17202>
- Cookey, Peter & Kugedera, Ziggy & Alamgir, Muhammed & Brdjanovic, Damir. (2020). Perception management of non-sewered sanitation systems towards scheduled faecal sludge emptying behaviour change intervention. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*. 7. 10.1057/s41599-020-00662-0.
- Conroy, K.M., and Mancl, K.M., 2022. Understanding the adoption of urine-diverting dry toilets (UDDTs) in low- and lower-middle-income countries using the Diffusion of Innovation framework. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene*

- for Development, Vol. 12 (12): 905–920. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2022.154>
- Costell, E., Tárrega, A., and Bayarri, S., 2010. Food Acceptance: The Role of Consumer Perception and Attitudes. *Chem. Percept.* 3:42–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12078-009-9057-1>
- Cronin, M. A., & George, E. (2023). The Why and How of the Integrative Review. *Organizational Research Methods*, 26(1), 168-192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428120935507>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Davis, F. D. (1993). User acceptance of information technology: System characteristics, user perceptions and behavioural impacts. *International Journal of Man-Machine Studies*, 38(3), 475–487. <https://doi.org/10.1006/imms.1993.1022>
- Dellstrom Rosenquist, L., E., 2005. A psychosocial analysis of the human-sanitation nexus. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Vol. 25 (3), pp. 335 – 346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2005.07.003>.
- Dery, J.L., Rock, C.M., Goldstein, R.R., Onumajuru, C., Brassill N., Zozaya, S., and Suri, M.R., 2019. Understanding grower perceptions and attitudes on the use of nontraditional water sources, including reclaimed or recycled water, in the semi-arid Southwest United States. *Environ Res.* 170:500-509. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2018.12.039. Epub 2018 Dec 18. PMID: 30703624. Accessed: 10 December 2024
- Devine, Jacqueline, 2009. Introducing SaniFOAM : a framework to analyze sanitation behaviors to design effective sanitation programs (English). Water and sanitation program working paper Washington, DC: World Bank. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/272351468334778050>
- Devault, M., Woolf, D., and Lehmann, J 2025. [Nutrient recycling potential of excreta for global crop and grassland production](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01467-8). *Nature Sustainability*, Nature, Vol. 8(1), pp 99-111. DOI: 10.1038/s41893-024-01467-8. Accessed: 21 June, 2025
- Diener, S., Semiyaga, S., Niwagaba, CB., Muspratt, AM., Gning, JB., Mbéguéré, M., Ennin, JE., Zurbrugg, C., Strande, L., 2014. A value proposition: Resource recovery from faecal sludge—Can it be the driver for improved sanitation? *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, Vol. 88, 32 - 38. ISSN 0921-3449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2014.04.005>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Dhollande S, Taylor A, Meyer S, Scott M. 2021. Conducting integrative reviews: a guide for novice nursing researchers. *J Res Nurs.* 2021 Aug;26(5):427-438. doi: 10.1177/1744987121997907. Epub 2021 Aug 5. PMID: 35251272; PMCID: PMC8894639. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Dideriksen, M., 2024. Fear of Pooping: Is it OCD, Coprophobia, or Anxiety? NOCD, Chicago, IL, USA. [Fear of pooping | NOCD](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-9800-0_10)
- Dijksterhuis, A., & van Knippenberg, A. (1998). The relation between perception and behaviour, or how to win a game of Trivial Pursuit. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 74(4), 865–877. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.74.4.865>
- Duncker LC, Matsebe GN. Prejudices and attitudes toward reuse of nutrients from urine diversion toilets in South Africa. Refereed Paper. 33rd Wedc International Conference, Accra, Ghana, 2008. Access to sanitation and safe water: Global Partnerships and local actions. 2008
- Duncker LC. Ownership and use of urine diversion sanitation systems in South Africa. CSIR research report No. CSIR/BE/IPDS/IR/2006/0049/B. Pretoria, South Africa. 2006
- Ejigu, A.K., and Yeshitela, K., 2024. Exploring the factors influencing urban farmers' perception and attitude toward the use of excreta-based organic fertilizers in Arba Minch City, Ethiopia. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.*, Vol. 7:1271811. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1271811>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Ekane, N., Mertz, C. K., Slovic, P., Kjellen, M., & Westlund, H. (2015). Risk and benefit judgment of excreta as fertilizer in agriculture: An exploratory investigation in Rwanda and Uganda. *Human and Ecology Risk Assessment*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2015.1100515>
- Eom, YS., Oh, H., Cho, J., and Kim, J., 2021. Social acceptance and willingness to pay for a smart Eco-toilet system

- producing a Community-based bioenergy in Korea. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, Vol. 47:101400. ISSN 2213-1388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101400>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Faria, D.C. & Naval, L.P. (2022) Wastewater reuse: Perception and social acceptance. *Water and Environment Journal*, 36(3), 433–447. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/wej.12776>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Ferguson, M.J., and Bargh, J.A., 2004. How social perception can automatically influence behaviour. *TRENDS in Cognitive Sciences*, Vol. 8:1. doi:10.1016/j.tics.2003.11.004
- Ferronato, N., Mendoza, I.J.C., Portillo, M.A.G., Conti, F., and Torretta, V., 2022. Are waste-based briquettes alternative fuels in developing countries? A critical review. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, Vol. 68, 220-241. ISSN 0973-0826. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2022.03.013>.
- Gitau, H., Chumo, I., Muindi, K., Simiyu, S., & Mberu, B. (2020). Awareness and attitudes towards the use of recycled faecal sludge products in Nairobi's slums. *Cities & Health*, 6(1), 149–158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23748834.2020.1804290>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Guo S, Wu Z, Wen L. Urban Residents' Acceptance Intention to Use Recycled Stormwater-An Examination of Values, Altruism, Social and Cultural Norms, and Perceived Health Risks. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022 Feb 28;19(5):2825. doi: 10.3390/ijerph19052825. PMID: 35270511; PMCID: PMC8910520. Accessed: 10 December 2024
- Gwara, S., Wale, E. and Odindo, A., 2022a. Behavioral intentions of rural farmers to recycle human excreta in agriculture. *Sci Rep* 12, 5890. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-09917-z>.
- Gwara S., Wale E., and Odindo A., 2022b. Psychometric analysis of the ecological dispositions of rural farming communities in South Africa: Implications for human excreta reuse in agriculture. *PLOS Sustainability and Transformation* 1(6): e0000019. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pstr.0000019>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Gwara, S.; Wale, E.; Odindo, A.; Buckley, C., 2021. Attitudes and Perceptions on the Agricultural Use of Human Excreta and Human Excreta Derived Materials: A Scoping Review. *Agriculture* 2021, 11, 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture11020153>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Gwara, S., Wale, E., Odindo, A., & Buckley, C. 2020. Why do We Know So Much and Yet So Little? A Scoping Review of Willingness to Pay for Human Excreta Derived Material in Agriculture. *Sustainability*, 12(16), 6490. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12166490>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Horlu, Godwin & Egbadzor, Kenneth Fafa & Afetorgbor, Emmanuel & Akumah, Asiwome. (2024). Perception of urine diverting dry toilet and baobab cultivation in Adaklu District of Ghana. *Sustainable Environment*. 10. 10.1080/27658511.2024.2391630
- Ignacio, J. J., Alvin Malenab, R., Pausta, C. M., Beltran, A., Belo, L., Tanhueco, R. M., Era, M., Eusebio, R. C., Promentilla, M. A., & Orbecido, A. (2018). Perceptions and Attitudes Toward Eco-Toilet Systems in Rural Areas: A Case Study in the Philippines. *Sustainability*, 10(2), 521. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10020521>
- Jenkins, J., 2005. *The Humanure Handbook: a guide to composting human manure*. Joseph Jenkins Inc, pp. 256, ISBN: 9780964425835
- Kabeyi, M.J.B., and Olanrewaju, O.A, 2022. Biogas Production and Applications in the Sustainable Energy Transition. *Hindawi Journal of Energy*, Vol. 2022, Article ID 8750221, PP. 43. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8750221>
- Khalid, A., 2018. Human excreta: a resource or a taboo? Assessing the socio-cultural barriers, acceptability, and reuse of human excreta as a resource in Kakul Village District Abbottabad, Northwestern Pakistan. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development* 1 March 2018; 8 (1): 71–80. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2017.019>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- King, L., 2021. Use and perception of biosolids through a literature review and a case study in Ndola, Zambia. University of Jyväskylä, Faculty of Mathematics and Science, Department of Biological and Environmental Science Master Thesis
- Kollmann J, Nath S, Singh S, Balasubramanian S, Reynaert E, Morgenroth E, Contzen N. Acceptance of on-site wastewater treatment and reuse in Bengaluru, India: The role of perceived costs, risks, and benefits. *Sci Total Environ*.

- 2023 Oct 15;895:165042. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165042. Epub 2023 Jun 23. PMID: 37355129. Accessed: 10 December 2024
- Koottatep, Thammarat & Cooney, Peter & Polprasert, Chongrak. (2019). *Regenerative Sanitation: A New Paradigm For Sanitation 4.0*. IWA Publishers, London, UK. 10.2166/9781780409689
- Kutcher, AM, LeBaron, VT, 2022. A simple guide for completing an integrative review using an example article, *Journal of Professional Nursing*, Vol. 40:13-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.profnurs.2022.02.004>. ISSN 8755-7223. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S8755722322000199>). Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Lagerkvist, C.J., Shikuku, K., Okello, J., Karanja, N., and Ackello-Ogutu, C., 2015. A conceptual approach for measuring farmers' attitudes to integrated soil fertility management in Kenya. *NJAS - Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences*, Vols 74–75, PP 17-26. ISSN 1573-5214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.njas.2015.06.001>.
- Lohman, H.A.C., Trimmer, J.T., Katende, D., Mubasira, M., Nagirinya, M., Nsereko, F., Banadda, N., Cusick, R.D., and Guest, J.S., 2020. Advancing Sustainable Sanitation and Agriculture through Investments in Human-Derived Nutrient Systems. *Environmental Science & Technology* 2020 54 (15), 9217-9227. DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.0c03764
- Mamera, M., van., JJ., Tol, Aghoghovwia, MP., and Mapetere, GT., 2020. Community Faecal Management Strategies and Perceptions on Sludge Use in Agriculture. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17: 4128. doi:10.3390/ijerph17114128. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Mariwah S, Drangert JO. Community perceptions of human excreta as fertilizer in peri-urban agriculture in Ghana. *Waste Manag Res*. 2011 Aug;29(8):815-22. doi: 10.1177/0734242X10390073. Epub 2011 Jan 17. PMID: 21242178
- Massoud, M.A., Kazarian, A., Alameddine, I. et al. Factors influencing the reuse of reclaimed water as a management option to augment water supplies. *Environ Monit Assess* 190, 531 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-018-6905-y>
- McConville, JR., Metson, GS., and Persson, H., 2023. Acceptance of human excreta derived fertilizers in Swedish grocery stores. *City and Environment Interactions*, Vol. 17:100096. ISSN 2590-2520. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cacint.2022.100096>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- McClaran N, Behe BK, Huddleston P, Fernandez RT. Recycled or reclaimed? The effect of terminology on water reuse perceptions. *J Environ Manage*. 2020 May 1;261:110144. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110144. Epub 2020 Feb 1. PMID: 32148255. Accessed: 10 December 2024
- Mkude, IT., Gabriellson, S., and Kimwaga, R., 2021. Knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) on fecal sludge resource recovery and reuse in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development* 11 (5): 758–770. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2021.249>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Moya, B., Parker, A., Sakrabani, R., Sakrabani, R., and Mesa, B., 2019. Evaluating the Efficacy of Fertilisers Derived from Human Excreta in Agriculture and Their Perception in Antananarivo, Madagascar. *Waste Biomass Valor* 10, 941–952. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-017-0113-9>
- Mugivhisa, L.L., & Olowoyo, J.O., & Mzimba, D.. (2017). Perceptions on organic farming and selected organic fertilizers by subsistence farmers in Ga-Rankuwa, Pretoria, South Africa. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*. 9. 1-7. 10.1080/20421338.2016.1269459
- Mugivhisa, L., and Olowoyo, J., 2015. An assessment of university students and staff perceptions regarding the use of human urine as a valuable soil nutrient in South Africa. *Afr. Health Sci*. 15 (3), 999. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v15i3.39>
- Müller, P., Pedro, JPB., and de Castro Freitas, CH., 2017. Farmer's Perception in the Central Amazon on the Agricultural use of Human Urine. *MUNDOAMAZÓNICO* 8(1): 101-114
- Mwamlima, P., Mayo, A.W., Gabriellson, S., Kimwaga, R., 2023. Potential use of faecal sludge derived char briquettes as an alternative cooking energy source in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: “Nexus between Sanitation and Energy (SDG 6 & 7)”. *Hygiene and Environmental Health Advances* 7:100068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heha.2023.100068>
- Naughton, CC., Akers, P., Yoder, D., Baer, R., and Mihelcic, JR., 2018. Can Sanitation Technology Play a Role in User Perceptions of Resource Recovery? An Evaluation of Composting Latrine Use in Developing World Communities in

- Panama. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52(20): 11803-11812. <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.est.8b02431>. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Nicholas, H.L.; Halfacree, K.H.; Mabbett, I., 2022. Public Perceptions of Faecal Sludge Biochar and Biosolids Use in Agriculture. *Sustainability* 14, 15385. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142215385>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Nimoh, F., Ohene-Yankyera, K., Poku, K., Konradsen, F., and Abaidoo, RC., 2014. Farmers' perception on excreta reuse for peri-urban agriculture in Southern Ghana. *Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics*, 6(10) 421-428. Article Number: 5047AFA47445. Doi: 10.5897/JDAE2014.0575. Accessed: 09 December 2024
- Oermann MH, Knafelz KA. Strategies for completing a successful integrative review. *Nurse Author Ed.* 2021; 31(3-4): 65-68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nae2.30>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Okem, AE., Xulu, S., Tilley, E., Buckley, C., and Roma, E., 2013. Assessing perceptions and willingness to use urine in agriculture: a case study from rural areas of eThekweni municipality, South Africa. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development* 1 December 2013; 3 (4): 582–591. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2166/washdev.2013.036>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Okem, A. E., & Odindo, A. O. 2020. Indigenous Knowledge and Acceptability of Treated Effluent in Agriculture. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9304. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219304>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Onabanjo, T., Patchigolla, K., Wagland, S.T., Fidalgo, B., Kolios, A., McAdam, E., Parker, A., Williams, L., Tyrrel, S., and Cartmell, E., 2016. Energy recovery from human faeces via gasification: A thermodynamic equilibrium modelling approach. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol 118, 364-376. ISSN 0196-8904. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2016.04.005>.
- Onwugbuezie, A.J., and Johnson, R.B., 2006. The “validity” issue in mixed research. *Research in the Schools* 13:48-63.
- Osei-Marfo, M., de Vries N. K., Awuah, E., 2021. People's perceptions on the use of human excreta for biogas generation in Ghana. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24:352–376 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01439-4>
- Page, MJ, McKenzie, JE, Bossuyt, PM, Boutron, I, Hoffmann, TC, Mulrow, CD, Shamseer, L, Tetzlaff, JM, Akl, EA, Brennan, SE, Chou, R, Glanville, J, Grimshaw, JM, Hróbjartsson, A, Lalu, MM, Li, T, Loder, EW, Mayo-Wilson, E, McDonald, S, McGuinness, LA, Stewart, LA, Thomas, J, Tricco, AC, Welch, VA, Whiting, P, and Moher, D, 2021. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews}, *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. BMJ Publishing Group Ltd. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>. <https://www.bmj.com/content/372/bmj.n71.full.pdf>. Accessed: 15 October 2024.
- Pishnyak, Alina & Khalina, Natal'ya. (2021). Perception of New Technologies: Constructing an Innovation Openness Index. *Foresight and STI Governance*. 15. 39-54. 10.17323/2500-2597.2021.1.39.54.
- Poortvliet PM, Sanders L, Weijma J, De Vries JR., 2018. Acceptance of new sanitation: The role of end-users' pro-environmental personal norms and risk and benefit perceptions. *Water Res.* 15;131:90-99. doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2017.12.032. Accessed: 10 December 2024
- Roma, E., Benoit, N., Buckley, C., & Bell, S. 2013a. Using the Receptivity model to uncover “urine blindness”: perceptions on the re-use of urine. *Waste Management & Research*, 31(6), 648–654.
- Roma, E, Philp, K, Buckley, C, Xulu, S and Scott, D, 2013b. User perceptions of urine diversion dehydration toilets: Experiences from a cross-sectional study in eThekweni Municipality. *Water SA*, Vol. 39 No. 2. African Journal Online. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/wsa.v39i2.15>
- Rose, C. & Parker, A. & Jefferson, Bruce & Cartmell, Elise. (2015). The Characterization of Feces and Urine: A Review of the Literature to Inform Advanced Treatment Technology. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*. 45. 00-00. 10.1080/10643389.2014.1000761. Accessed: January 11, 2025
- Roxburgh, H., Hampshire, K., Tilley, EA., Oliver, DM., and Quilliam, RS., 2020. Being shown samples of composted, granulated faecal sludge strongly influences acceptability of its use in peri-urban subsistence agriculture. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling: X*, Volume 7, 100041. ISSN 2590-289X. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2020.100041>.

Accessed: 08 December 2024

Simha, P., Lalander, C., Vinnerås, B., and Ganesapillai, M., 2017. Farmer attitudes and perceptions to the re-use of fertiliser products from resource-oriented sanitation systems – The case of Vellore, South India. *Science of The Total Environment*, Vols 581–582:885-896. ISSN 0048-9697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.01.044>. Accessed: 08 December 2024

Simha, P., Barton, MA., Perez-Mercado, LF., McConville, JR., Lalander, C., Magri, ME., Dutta, S., Kabir, H., Selvakumar, A., Zhou, X., Martin, T., Kizos, T., Kataki, R., Gerchman, Y., Herscu-Kluska, R., Alrousan, D., Goh, EG., Elenciuc, D., Głowacka, A., Korculanin, L., Tzeng, RV., Ray, SS., Niwagaba, C., Prouty, C., Mihelcic, JR., Vinnerås, B., 2021. Willingness among food consumers to recycle human urine as crop fertiliser: Evidence from a multinational survey. *Science of The Total Environment*. Vol. 765:144438. ISSN 0048-9697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144438>. Accessed: 10 December 2024

Singh, S.; Ibrahim, M.A.; Pawar, S.; Brdjanovic, D., 2022. Public Perceptions of Reuse of Faecal Sludge Co-Compost in Bhubaneswar, India. *Sustainability*, 14, 4489. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084489>. Accessed: 08 December 2024

Śniatała, B., Al-Hazmi, H.E., Sobotka, D., Zhai, J., and Maĳinia, J., 2024. Advancing sustainable wastewater management: A comprehensive review of nutrient recovery products and their applications. *Science of The Total Environment*, Vol. 937, 173446. ISSN 0048-9697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173446>

Souza MT, Silva MD, Carvalho RD., 2010. Integrative review: what is it? How to do it? *Einstein (Sao Paulo)* 8(1):102-6. doi: 10.1590/S1679-45082010RW1134. PMID: 26761761. Accessed: 08 December 2024

[Statista Research Department](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1224205/forecast-of-the-total-population-of-africa/), Mar 22, 2024. Forecast of the total population of Africa 2020-2050. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1224205/forecast-of-the-total-population-of-africa/>. Accessed: January 11, 2025

Subedi, M., Matthews, R.B., Pogson, M., Abegaz, A., Balana, B.B., Oyesiku-Blakemore, J., and Smith, J., 2014. Can biogas digesters help to reduce deforestation in Africa? *Biomass and Bioenergy*, Vol. 70:87-98. ISSN 0961-9534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2014.02.029>.

Surendra, K.C., Takara, D., Hashimoto, A.G., Khanal, S.K., 2014. Biogas as a sustainable energy source for developing countries: Opportunities and challenges. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 31:846–859. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.12.015>

The Water Page.com, 2025. The History and Evolution of Ecological Sanitation Practices. <https://thewaterpage.com/the-history-and-evolution-of-ecological-sanitation-practices/>

Uddin, SM.N., Muhandiki, V.S., Sakai, A., Al Mamun, A., and Hridi, S.M., 2014. Socio-cultural acceptance of appropriate technology: Identifying and prioritizing barriers for widespread use of the urine diversion toilets in rural Muslim communities of Bangladesh. *Technology in Society*, Vol. 38, pp 32-39. ISSN 0160-791X. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2014.02.002>.

UNDESA (2024). *World Population Prospects 2024: Summary of Results*. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (UNDESA/POP/2024/TR/NO. 9). Accessed: January 11, 2025

van den Broek S, Nybom I, Hartmann M, Doetterl S, Garland G., 2024. Opportunities and challenges of using human excreta-derived fertilizers in agriculture: A review of suitability, environmental impact and societal acceptance. *Sci Total Environ*. 2024 Nov 12;957:177306. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.177306. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 39515389. Accessed: 10 December 2024

Vandeginste, V., Lim, C., & Ji, Y. (2024). Exploratory Review on Environmental Aspects of Enhanced Weathering as a Carbon Dioxide Removal Method. *Minerals*, 14(1), 75. <https://doi.org/10.3390/min14010075>

Warner, K. J., & Jones, G. A. (2018). Energy and Population in Sub-Saharan Africa: Energy for Four Billion? *Environments*, 5(10), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments5100107>

Werkneh, A.A., and Gebru, S.,B., 2023. Development of ecological sanitation approaches for integrated recovery of biogas, nutrients and clean water from domestic wastewater. *Resources, Environment and Sustainability*, Vol. 11,

100095. ISSN 2666-9161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resenv.2022.100095>. Accessed: April 17, 2025
- Whittemore R, Knafl K. 2005. The integrative review: updated methodology. *J Adv Nurs*. 2005 Dec;52(5):546-53. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2648.2005.03621.x. PMID: 16268861. 15 October 2024
- Wilde BC, Lieberherr E, Pereira E, Odindo A and Six J (2022) A participatory assessment of nitrified urine fertilizer use in Swayimane, South Africa: Crop production potential, farmer attitudes and smallholder challenges. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst*. 6:781879. doi: 10.3389/fsufs.2022.781879
- Williams, NB., Quilliam, RS., Campbell, B., Ghatani, R., and Dickie, J., 2022. Taboos, toilets and biogas: Socio-technical pathways to acceptance of a sustainable household technology. *Energy Research & Social Science*, Vol. 86:102448. ISSN 2214-6296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102448>. Accessed: 08 December 2024
- Winbland, U., and Simpson-Hebert, M., 2004. *Ecological Sanitation: revised and enlarged edition*. Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI), Sweden. https://www.susana.org/_resources/documents/default/2-487-winblad-et-al-2004-ecological-sanitation-sei-en.pdf. ISBN: 9188714985
- Wong, G., Greenhalgh, T., Westhorp, G., Buckingham, J., and Pawson, R., 2013. RAMESES publication standards: meta-narrative reviews. *BMC Med* 11, 20 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7015-11-20>. Accessed: 15 October 2024
- Zeldovich, L. (2021). *The Other Dark Matter: The Science and Business of Turning Waste into Wealth and Health*. University of Chicago Press
- Zeldovich, L. (2012). Getting Minds Out of the Sewer. *Science*, 337(6095), 679-680.